

science and policy
for a healthy future

Report on workshop about opportunities and obstacles for linking HBM and health studies

Deliverable Report

D11.2

WP11 - Linking HBM, health studies and registers

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1 Authors and acknowledgements

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2 Glossary

CHMS	Canadian Health Measures Survey
EHES	European Health Examination Survey ¹
EHIS	European Health Interview Survey
ENNS	French National Nutrition and Health Survey
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
GerES	German Environmental Survey
HBM	Human Biomonitoring
HES	Health examination survey
HSE	Health Survey for England
KiGGS	German Health Interview and Examination Survey for Children and Adolescents
SOP	Standard operating procedure
QA	Quality assurance

¹ <http://www.ehes.info>

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3 Summary

Human biomonitoring (HBM) and health studies, such as health examination surveys (HES), have many common features in data collection. Thereby, combining the collection of HBM and health data provides possible synergies.

A workshop on opportunities and obstacles for linking HBM and health studies was organized on 14–15 June 2018 in Brussels, Belgium, to discuss country experiences and theoretical background about this type of linkage. A total of 60 participants from 20 countries registered for the workshop.

Presentations and discussions of the workshop can be summarized in two lists; one about benefits and one about challenges related to linking of HBM and health studies.

Benefits of combining HBM and health study

- Use on existing survey infrastructure on
 - recruitment of participants,
 - collection of biological samples and conducting health examinations, and
 - collection of data through questionnaires on wide range of topics from health, health behaviours, socio-economic position and exposure pathways.
- Synergies in public relations activities during the fieldwork.
- Reputation and awareness of the studies in the public.
- Chance to combine data on exposure, health behaviours, health and socio-economic position to large, comprehensive data sets.
- Reduced costs of public resources.

Challenges for combining HBM and health study

- Partners involved in HBM and health studies may have different priorities. Finding a balanced compromise between them is often needed.
- Preparation phase may take longer time than for individual HBM and health study due to the need for more negotiations, meetings and agreements (rights, duties, sharing of costs, data protection and sharing, etc.).
- Target population, time lines, extent of the full survey etc. may be defined by HES study. Accommodating a HBM part to this may be challenging.
- Volume of collected blood samples is limited. How is the use of the collected samples prioritised in relation to HBM and health parts' requirements?
- To minimize the burden on the participants, the length of the questionnaire must be limited. On the other hand, it should include all relevant questions on both HBM and health issues.
- Coordination between HBM and health modules of the study.
- The large data sets with information on exposures and health that are generated by the combined studies are often underutilized.

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All provided country presentations and theoretical background information strongly support a feasibility to combine HBM and health studies. If it is not possible to include the HBM module to be carried out among the entire HES sample, which often is relatively large in national HESs (4000 persons and above), it should be considered if it would be sufficient to have the HBM module carried out among a sub-sample of the whole sample. The collaboration between HBM and health communities could also start through the use of stored biological samples from health studies and slowly, with increased knowledge, grow into full-size collaboration from planning to reporting.

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4 Introduction

The European Human Biomonitoring Initiative (HBM4EU) is a joint effort of 28 countries (24 European Member States, three associated countries and Switzerland), the European Environment Agency and the European Commission, co-funded under Horizon 2020.

The main objective of HBM4EU is to use human biomonitoring (HBM) to assess human exposure to chemicals in Europe in order to better understand the associated health impacts and to improve chemical risk assessment. HBM4EU will generate knowledge on chemical exposure levels in the population and their health effects.

Several European countries have experience in conducting HBM studies, although the geographical coverage varies between countries. In parallel, health examination surveys (HES) are conducted in many European countries at the national or regional level. Population-based health studies targeted on specific diseases or population groups are also conducted in many European countries. HBM and health studies, such as HESs, have many common features in data collection. Both study types have survey based data collection with similarities in sample selection and recruitment, ethics and data protection, questionnaires, collection of biological samples and also to some extent on objective health measurements.

Under WP11, one of the tasks has been to evaluate opportunities and obstacles related to combining HBM and health studies at the national level. To obtain information on how HBM or health study investigators/principle investigators would see possible opportunities and obstacles of such a combination, a questionnaire was launched towards the end of 2017 and updated in early 2018. Results from this questionnaire served as a base for further discussions. The results were presented in Deliverable Report D11.1 (Report on opportunities and obstacles of combining HBM and health studies, availability of health studies with biological samples, availability of administrative registers, and guidelines for combining HBM and health studies).

To facilitate more interactive discussion, a workshop on opportunities and obstacles on combining HBM and health studies was organized on 14–15 June 2018 in Brussels, Belgium. The aim of this workshop was to look into ways how HBM and health studies could be combined to obtain synergies in the use of common infrastructures and personnel, and at the same time obtaining more information on study subjects and conducting more cost-effective data collection. In the workshop, experiences from countries which already have combined HBM and health studies were presented, and existing HBM and health survey protocols for their similarities and differences were compared.

The workshop was targeted for everyone interested to

- include more health measures to their existing HBM study,
- include more HBM measurements to their health survey, or
- plan a new combined HBM and health survey.

5 Workshop - general information

5.1 Agenda

Thursday 14 June 2018

Time	Title	Speaker
12:00-13:00	Registration	
13:00-13:10	Welcome and introduction to the workshop	Hanna Tolonen THL, Finland
13:10-13:25	Introduction to the HBM4EU project	Marika Kolossa UBA, Germany
13:25-13:55	Summary of the results from the 'obstacles and opportunities questionnaire'	Sónia Namorado INSA, Portugal
13:55-15:20	Experiences from countries which have already combined HBM and health studies	
13:55-14:20	Germany	Marika Kolossa UBA, Germany and Antje Gößwald RKI, Germany
14:20-14:40	France	Loïc Rambaud Public Health France
14:40-15:00	Canada	Kate Werry Health Canada
15:00-15:20	Discussion	
15:20-15:50	<i>Coffee break</i>	
15:50-17:30	Expectations and reservations from countries without combined HBM and health studies	
15:50-16:10	Slovenia	Milena Horvat JSI, Slovenia
16:10-16:30	Belgium	Greet Schoeters VITO, Belgium
16:30-16:50	Denmark	Allan Linneberg RegionH, Denmark
16:50-17:10	UK/England	Jennifer Mindel UCL, UK
17:10-17:30	Discussion	
17:30-17:45	Summary and conclusions	
17:45-18:45	<i>Reception</i>	

Friday 15 June 2018

Time	Title	Speaker
9:00-9:10	Objectives of the day	Hanna Tolonen
9:10-10:50	Commonalities and differences between HBM and health studies	
9:10-9:30	Ethics and data protection	Lisbeth Knudsen UCPH, Denmark
9:30-9:50	Sampling and recruitment	Hanna Tolonen THL, Finland
9:50-10:10	Questionnaires	Ana Virgolino FMUL, Portugal
10:10-10:30	Collection of biological samples	Anna-Maria Andersson RegionH, Denmark
10:30-10:50	Objective health measurements	Loïc Rambaud Public Health France
10:50-11:20	<i>Coffee break</i>	
11:20-12:00	Available training	
11:20-11:40	Training on HBM issues	Paul Scheepers RUMC, Netherlands
11:40-12:00	Training on health measurements	Hanna Tolonen THL, Finland
12:00-12:45	Round table discussion (speakers of Thursday)	Moderated by Hanna Tolonen
12:45-13:00	Summing up and closer of the workshop	

5.2 Participants

The invitation to the workshop was published at the HBM4EU website (both internal and public). Workshop was open for both HBM4EU partners as well as for interested persons outside the consortium.

Altogether 60 participants from 20 countries registered to the workshop (see Figure 1).

Figure 1: Map of countries (in green), which were represented at the Workshop on 14–15 June, 2018

The following countries were represented (number of participants in brackets): Austria (2), Belgium (22), Canada (1), Cyprus (1), Denmark (3), Finland (2), France (3), Germany (6), Greece (1), Hungary (1), Iceland (1), Israel (1), Italy (6), Latvia (1), the Netherlands (2), Portugal (2), Slovakia (1), Slovenia (1), Sweden (1), the UK (2). Most of the registered participants (47 out of 60) were members of the HBM4EU consortium.

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6 Key messages of the presentations

6.1 Welcome and introduction to the workshop

Hanna Tolonen, the leader of WP11, from the National Institute for Health and Welfare (THL), Finland opened the workshop with a short introduction to the aims of the workshop.

HBM and health surveys have a lot of common features. Both study types aim for better health and wellbeing of the population and at the same time through better health to increase productivity. Measurement of lifestyle factors such as diet, smoking, use of cosmetics, physical activity etc. will provide information on exposures to substances of interest for HBM but also in health surveys about risk factors of health outcomes.

Currently, in many countries HBM and health surveys follow their own separate tracks even though there would be evident synergies and added value for their combination. This workshop focused on these synergies and added value.

HBM4EU

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**Linking HBM and
health studies.**

What are possible
opportunities and
obstacles?

**14-15 June 2018, Brussels,
Belgium**

Workshop on linking HBM and health studies,
14-15 June 2019, Brussels, Belgium

Twitter: @HBM4EU, #HBM_HES,
@tolonen_hanna

Workshop on linking HBM and health studies,
14-15 June 2019, Brussels, Belgium

Twitter: @HBM4EU, #HBM_HES,
@tolonen_hanna

Common interest

Exposures

Workshop on linking HBM and health studies,
14-15 June 2019, Brussels, Belgium

Two tracks coming together

Workshop on linking HBM and health studies,
14-15 June 2019, Brussels, Belgium

Twitter: @HBM4EU, #HBM_HES,
@tolonen_hanna

Synergies

- Joint fieldwork, better value for money
- Recruitment of invitees
 - Time consuming phase
- Once people are recruited to survey
 - Additional questionnaires
 - Additional measurements
 - Extra tubes of blood/urine

Added value

- More information on same people
 - Background information
 - Health determinants and behaviours
 - Health
 - Environmental exposures
- Comparability of the results between different type of surveys on common outcomes/indicators

Workshop programme – Day 1

- Summary of results for HBM4EU, WP11 questionnaire on opportunities and obstacles on combining HBM and health studies
- Country experiences
 - 3 presentations on how combining have been done
 - 4 presentations on what are expected opportunities and obstacles if combination would be done

Workshop on linking HBM and health studies,
14-15 June 2019, Brussels, Belgium

Workshop programme – Day 2

- In theory
 - Ethics and data protection
 - Sampling and recruitment
 - Questionnaires
 - Collection of biological samples
 - Objective health measurements
- Available training

Workshop on linking HBM and health studies,
14-15 June 2019, Brussels, Belgium

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@HBM4EU, #HBM_HES

<http://www.hbm4eu.eu>

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 733032.

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6.2 Introduction to the HBM4EU project

Marike Kolossa-Gehring, the coordinator of the HBM4EU project from the German Environment Agency (UBA) provided a short introduction to the HBM4EU project. Her presentation highlighted the structure, contents and objectives of this large, EU-wide project.

Project overview

Timeframe and budget:

- 5 years (2017-2021)
- European Joint Programme under Horizon 2020
- Total budget: € 74 million

28 countries and the European Environment Agency:

- 24 EU Member States
- 3 associated countries
- Switzerland

Coordinated by the German Environment Agency (UBA)

Building the science policy interface in HBM4EU

Transparency and participation

Developing a prioritisation strategy

National Hubs: Future Support and Resource for HBM4EU

- Involved in all aspects of HBM4EU
- Capacity building at national level
- Outcome: Connected foundations for a sustainable pan-European HBM platform that builds on national hubs and existing expertise

Collect EU wide HBM data

Science policy

Objective 1:

Assessing the actual exposure of EU population or differences between EU countries

Objective 2:

Monitoring time trends in exposure

Objective 3:

Assessing the impact of policy

Theoretical concept:

Sampling frame to achieve EU representative samples

! All sampling strategies are compromises

Domains for which reliable data are **needed**:

Age	Sex	Geographical coverage
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ North ✓ East ✓ South ✓ West Europe 		

Domains for which reliable data are **wanted**:

Education: ISCED-classification	Subject living environment	Other?
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ SES ✓ - 		

WP9 – Laboratory analysis and Quality Assurance: ICI/EQUAS 2018

Group	Compounds	Matrix	No. Labs invited
Phthalates	MEP, MBzP, MiBP, MnBP, MCHP, MnPeP, MEHP, 3OH-MEHP, 3oxo-MEHP, 5α-MEPP, MnOP, OH-MiNP, α-MiNP, OH-MiDP, α-MiDP	Urine	26
DINCH	OH-MiNCH, α-MiNCH	Urine	10
Bisphenols	BPA, BPF, BPS	Urine	33
PFAS	78 exposure biomarkers /round 3 rounds (2 ICI+ 1 EQUAS) 7 organizing labs: preparing, testing, sending Control Material/analyzing-communicating results. 216 participating labs		
FRs			
PAHs			
Anilines	hydroxyphenanthrene, 2-hydroxyphenanthrene, 3-hydroxyphenanthrene, 4-hydroxyphenanthrene, 9-hydroxyphenanthrene, 1-PYR, 3-hydroxybenzo(a)pyrene MDA, MOCA, Aniline, p-aminophenol, MDA, N-acetyl-4-aminophenol, p-PDA, o-toluidine, 2,4-TDA, 2,6-TDA	Urine	14
Cd		Urine and blood	38
Cr		RBC, urine, plasma	16

12

Make HBM data available in IPCHEM

13

HBM4EU Website

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PUBLICATIONS

PEER REVIEWED PUBLICATIONS

DELIVERABLES

Deliverable 9.4 The Quality Assurance/Quality Control Scheme in the HBM4EU project
 Responsible author: Thomas Goen (FRAGUM), Co-authors: Holger Koch (FR), Argelia Castaño and Marta Esteban (SCIR), Juan Philippe Artigraç (INRA), Adrian Covari (J.Arteberg), Jana Klárová (ML) 11/2017

Additional Deliverable 11.1 How can the results from BRIDGE Health be incorporated to the work of HBM4EU?
 Responsible author: Madlen David (UBA), Co-authors: Anna-Maria Andersson (RegionH), Hanna Tolonen (THL) 10/2017

Additional Deliverable 12.1 Database of exposure-related and ancillary data for priority substances
 Responsible authors: Alberto Gotti (IUISS), Dana Sarganidis (AUTH), Co-authors: Evangelos Handakas (AUTH), Marco Perino (AUTH), Spyros Karakostas (AUTH) 10/2017

All HBM4EU publications available in a timely manner and freely accessible on the website!

round of substances
 Responsible author: Cathrine Thomsen (NPH), Co-authors: Enrique Ceguera, Octavio Pérez Lucarini, Monika Kasper-Sonnenberg, Holger Koch, Line S. Haug 09/2017

CALENDAR | NOV 2017

HIGHLIGHTS

HBM4EU is delighted to be collaborating with the European, Middle Eastern and African Society for Substancing and Depressivation - ESSSD.

Full methodology of paper published in German Environmental Survey for Children and Adolescents 2014 2017 (GwES 1) - the environmental module of KOOB Wave 2

HELR Scientific Symposium - New horizons for Early Life Exposome Research, 30-31 October 2017, Programme

Stakeholder workshop on prioritisation, Monday 20 November, Brussels, Belgium, Workshop agenda

Many thanks to our wonderful HBM4EU partners

Thank you for your attention!

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6.3 Summary of the results from the ‘obstacles and opportunities questionnaire’

Sónia Namorado from Instituto Nacional de Saúde Doutor Ricardo Jorge (INSA), Portugal, presented the results from the questionnaire launched by Task 11.1 about opportunities and obstacles on combining HBM and health studies.

Human biomonitoring and health studies are very similar in terms of the infrastructure and procedures necessary for their implementation, in both types of studies, data is collected through fieldwork, which constitutes one of the largest expenditures for such studies. Combined studies could then result in more cost-effective ways to conduct health and environmental monitoring.

Within the HBM4EU project, the advantages and obstacles of combined studies are being evaluated. With the aim of identifying opportunities and obstacles related to linking HBM, health surveys and administrative data sources, and to perform an inventory of the health studies available which could include a HBM component, an inventory of the recently conducted, ongoing and planned studies was produced.

Data from 58 different studies was reported and included in this inventory. Half of the studies were longitudinal and present the possibility of introducing a HBM component in the future rounds. The majority of the studies (63%) had more than 1000 participants and half of them were conducted only once (cross-sectional). Most of the reported studies had public funding, either from the government or from public grants (national or European).

The vast majority of the studies included the collection of biological samples (85%) and the storage of these samples for future use (93%), posing the opportunity to use them for the analyses of chemicals of interest. The most frequently stored biological samples were blood, plasma, serum and DNA. A little over half of the studies (63%) reported that the measurement of chemicals was performed or is planned to be performed in the future. The most frequently measured chemicals were phthalates, bisphenols and cadmium.

The majority of studies included clinical examinations (83%), clinical biomarkers (78%) and questionnaire data (100%). However, register data were retrieved for less than half of the studies (38%). The possibility to access register data was only reported by less than half (48%) of the studies that presently did not retrieve this type of data. More than half of the studies (58%) had ethical approval which allowed the measurement of chemicals in the collected samples and the majority of the ones that didn't have ethical approval (60%) considered that this approval would be possible to obtain.

Only a quarter of the studies combining HBM and HES have reported the occurrence of obstacles, shortcomings and difficulties in linking HBM and HES. Financial, logistic and legal issues were reported. Experience in overcoming obstacles related to linking HBM and HES highlighted the importance of adequate planning that includes both components from the beginning.

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Summary of the results from the “obstacles and opportunities questionnaire”

Sónia Namorado
INSA, Portugal

Studies reported

- 34 researchers
- 58 different studies

Type of study	Frequency	Percent
A health examination survey (HES)	16	28
A targeted health study (e.g. focusing on specific diseases, age-groups or other population subgroups)	15	26
An occupational health survey	3	5
A dietary survey/health interview survey (HIS)	2	3
A human biomonitoring survey (HBM)	5	9
A combined HES and HBM survey	14	24
Other	3	5
Total	58	100

14/06/2018

Studies reported

- 34 researchers
- 58 different studies

Type of study	Frequency	Percent
A health examination survey (HES)	16	28
A targeted health study (e.g. focusing on specific diseases, age-groups or other population subgroups)	15	26
An occupational health survey	3	5
A dietary survey/health interview survey (HIS)	2	3
A human biomonitoring survey (HBM)	5	9
A combined HES and HBM survey	14	24
Other	3	5
Total	58	100

14/06/2018

Studies characteristics and design

- 14 studies (26%) out of 54 studies were part of multinational collaborations
- majority (66%) initiated or planned to be initiated after 2010
- 20 studies (38%) finished between 2012 and 2017
(22 studies (42%) will be finished by 2020)
- majority (65%) reported a reference to a basic report or scientific publication about the study design
- 18 studies (45%) out of 40 studies had a representative sample of the general population
- 36 studies (90%) included both genders
- 11 studies (28%) had a maximum age inferior to 40 years old

14/06/2018

Studies characteristics and design

- 18 studies (45%) were cross-sectional and
19 studies (48%) were longitudinal

Type of study \ Study design	Cross-sectional	Longitudinal	Case-control	Other	Total number of studies
A health examination survey (HES)	11	9	1	4	16
A targeted health study	5	7	3	0	15
An occupational health survey	1	2	0	0	3
A human biomonitoring survey (HBM)	5	0	0	0	5
Other	0	1	0	0	1
Total	22	19	4	4	40

14/06/2018

3

Studies characteristics and design

- 25 studies (63%) had more than 1000 participants

Type of study \ Study size	< 100	100 - 249	250 - 999	≥ 1000	Total number of studies
A health examination survey (HES)	1	0	1	14	16
A targeted health study	0	7	1	7	15
An occupational health survey	1	1	0	1	3
A human biomonitoring survey (HBM)	0	0	3	2	5
Other	0	0	0	1	1
Total	2	8	5	25	40

14/06/2018

6

Studies characteristics and design

- 20 studies (50%) were repeated

Type of study \ Study frequency	Conducted only once	Repeated	Total number of studies
A health examination survey (HES)	8	8	16
A targeted health study	6	9	15
An occupational health survey	2	1	3
A human biomonitoring survey (HBM)	4	1	5
Other	0	1	1
Total	20	20	40

14/06/2018

Funding sources

- 20 studies (50%) had only one funding source (40% had 2)

Type of study \ Funding source	Government	Public grants	Private grants	EU grants or international R&D programmes	Other	Total number of studies
A health examination survey (HES)	10	6	3	7	2	16
A targeted health study	4	10	3	7	1	15
An occupational health survey	2	1	0	0	1	3
A human biomonitoring survey (HBM)	3	1	0	1	1	5
Other	0	1	0	0	1	1
Total	19	19	6	15	6	40

14/06/2018

Collection of biological samples

In the studies without an HBM component

	Frequency	Percent
Yes	33	85
No	6	15
Total	39	100

Could biological samples be collected?

	Frequency	Percent
Yes	2	33
No	1	17
Unknown	3	50
Total	6	100

14/06/2018

Collection of biological samples

Type of study	Collection of biological samples	Total number of studies
A health examination survey (HES)	15	16
A targeted health study	15	15
An occupational health survey	2	3
A dietary survey/health interview survey (HIS)	0	2
A human biomonitoring survey (HBM)	5	5
A combined HES and HBM survey	14	14
Other	1	3
1. Total	52	58

Storage of biological samples

- 37 studies (93%) stored or planned to store biological samples for future use

Type of study \ Samples	Blood	Plasma	Serum	DNA	Spot urine	1st morning urine	Total number of studies
A health examination survey (HES)	8	14	13	10	4	3	16
A targeted health study	11	7	7	10	8	7	15
An occupational health survey	0	1	0	0	0	0	3
A human biomonitoring survey (HBM)	4	2	2	1	3	2	5
Other	1	1	1	0	1	0	1
Total	24	25	23	21	16	12	40

14/06/2018

Measurement of chemicals

- 25 studies measured or planned to measure chemicals in the collected samples

Measurement \ Storage	Yes		No		Unknown	
	Frequency	Percent	Frequency	Percent	Frequency	Percent
Yes	24	65	8	22	5	14
No	1	50	1	50	0	0
Unknown	0	0	0	0	1	100
Total	25	63	9	23	6	15

14/06/2018

Measurement of chemicals

Chemicals Type of study	Phthalates	Bisphenols	PFCs	Flame retardants	Cd	PAHs	Anilines	Total number of studies
A health examination survey (HES)	1	2	1	0	2	2	0	16
A targeted health study	9	7	4	3	6	2	3	15
An occupational health survey	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	3
A human biomonitoring survey (HBM)	4	4	3	4	5	3	0	5
Other	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	1
Total	15	14	8	7	14	7	3	40

14/06/2018

Reasons for not measuring chemicals

	Frequency	Percent
Not considered relevant for the aim of the study	3	33
Lack of knowledge of relevance of measuring chemicals in relation to the aim of the study	0	0
Fear that it would affect recruitment/participation rate	0	0
Lack of funding for additional sample collection for measurement of chemicals	5	56
Lack of funding for laboratory analysis of chemicals	5	56
Collection of additional samples for chemical measurements logistically not practical	2	22
Lack of storage space of additional samples for chemical measurements	2	22
Lack of knowledge regarding collection and handling of samples for measurement of chemicals	1	11
Lack of capacity available for measurement of chemicals (laboratories, methods etc.)	1	11
Lack of funding for measurement of chemicals	2	22
Other reasons	2	22

Clinical examinations

- 33 studies (83%) included clinical examinations

Type of study \ Clinical examinations	Anthropometric measures	Blood pressure	Functional tests	Neurological tests	Other	Total number of studies
A health examination survey (HES)	16	16	8	4	10	16
A targeted health study	11	7	6	6	5	15
An occupational health survey	1	0	0	0	1	3
A human biomonitoring survey (HBM)	3	1	1	0	0	5
Other	1	1	0	0	1	1
Total	32	25	15	10	17	40

14/06/2018

Clinical biomarkers

- 31 studies (78%) included clinical biomarkers

Type of study \ Markers	Metabolic	Reproductive	Liver function	Kidney function	Thyroid function	Other	Total number of studies
A health examination survey	14	1	7	10	4	5	16
A targeted health study	5	5	1	4	6	4	15
An occupational health survey	0	0	1	0	0	2	3
A HBM survey	1	0	1	2	0	1	5
Other	1	0	0	0	0	0	1
Total	21	6	10	16	10	12	40

14/06/2018

Health outcomes & Questionnaire data

- 19 studies (48%) included health outcomes
- 40 studies (100%) included questionnaire data

Questionnaire data Type of study	Medical history	Current health	Lifestyle	Dietary habits	Occupational info	Socio-economic info	Total number of studies
A health examination survey	13	15	16	13	12	16	16
A targeted health study	11	11	14	13	10	14	15
An occupational health survey	2	3	3	1	3	2	3
A human biomonitoring survey (HBM)	3	3	5	5	2	4	5
Other	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
Total	30	33	39	33	28	37	40

14/06/2018

Register data

- 15 studies (38%) retrieved register data

Register Type of study	Mortality	Cancer-specific	Hospital admissions	Diabetes	Occupational	Other	Total number of studies
A health examination survey (HES)	6	5	5	4	1	5	16
A targeted health study	2	1	3	1	3	3	15
An occupational health survey	1	0	1	0	1	1	3
A human biomonitoring survey (HBM)	0	0	0	0	0	0	5
Other	0	0	0	0	0	1	1
Total	9	6	9	5	5	10	40

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Register data

- 12 studies (48%) out of 25 studies that didn't retrieved register data could do it

Type of study \ Register	Mortality	Cancer-specific	Hospital admissions	Diabetes	Occupational	Total number of studies
A health examination survey (HES)	4	1	1	1	0	4
A targeted health study	4	3	6	2	1	6
An occupational health survey	1	1	1	1	0	1
A human biomonitoring survey (HBM)	0	1	1	1	0	1
Other	0	0	0	0	0	0
Total	9	6	9	5	1	12

14/06/2018

Ethical approval

- 20 studies (58%) have ethical approval for the measurement of chemicals

Type of study \ Chemicals	Ethical approval	Phthalates	BPA's	PFCs	Flame retardants	Cd	PAHs	Anilines	Metals	Total number of studies
A HES	6	0	1	0	1	1	2	0	1	16
A targeted health study	12	10	9	7	7	8	7	7	4	15
Occupational health survey	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	3
Other	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
Total	20	10	10	7	8	9	9	7	6	35

- 9 studies (60%) out of 15 studies that don't have ethical approval could obtain it

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Ethical approval

Samples that can be used for the measurement of chemicals according to the ethical approval

Samples Type of study	Blood	Plasma	Serum	DNA	Spot urine	1st morning urine	Human milk	Hair	Umbilical cord blood	Total number of studies
A HES	2	3	2	1	2	1	0	1	0	6
A targeted health study	7	6	4	2	6	5	3	2	3	12
Occupational health survey	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	0	1
Other	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	1
Total	10	10	7	3	10	7	4	4	3	20

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Obstacles

- 3 studies (25%) out of 12 combined HBM + HES studies reported the following obstacles:

Obstacles	Frequency	Percent
Financial issues	1	33
Logistic issues (e.g. laboratory, human resources)	2	67
Legislation issues	3	100
Difficulties in recruitment of participants	1	33
Lack of knowledge on HBM or HES issues	0	0
Problems with ethical approval	0	0
Not seen important by policy makers/stakeholders	0	0
Other reasons	2	67

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Instituto **Nacional de Saúde**
Doutor Ricardo Jorge

Summary of the results from the “obstacles and opportunities questionnaire”

Workshop: Linking HBM and health studies. What are possible opportunities and obstacles?

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 733032.

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6.4 Experiences from countries which have already combined HBM and health studies

6.4.1 Germany

Antje Gößwald from Robert Koch-Institute (RKI), Germany and Marike Kolossa-Gehring from German Environment Agency (UBA) presented German joint effort of two organizations for combining HBM and health surveys.

The Robert Koch Institute (RKI) and the German Environment Agency (UBA) have a longstanding experience in combining health examination surveys (HES) and human biomonitoring surveys (HBM). Since 1985, five combined surveys have been conducted; three surveys focusing mainly on the adult population and two focusing on children and adolescents. The latest survey combining the German Health Interview and Examination Survey for Children and Adolescents (KiGGS Wave 2) and the German Environmental Survey for Children and Adolescents (GerES V) was completed in June 2017. A detailed description of KiGGS Wave 2² and GerES V³ survey contents and procedures can be found in the Journal of Health Monitoring. Briefly, in KiGGS Wave 2 data were collected on health status, health-related behaviour, psychosocial risk and protective factors, health care and living conditions, and health related measurements (i.e. anthropometrics, blood pressure measurement, spirometry, motor function, physical fitness and activity), and blood and urine sampling was performed. Subsequently, personal contact data and blood specimens of KiGGS Wave 2 participants who were also willing to participate in GerES V were transferred to UBA. UBA's contractor for fieldwork arranged a date for a home visit with all individual GerES V participants a few weeks later. During the home visit, morning urine, drinking water and ultrafine particulate matter samples were collected, outdoor noise was recorded and questionnaires were administered for identifying factors influencing the exposure to environmental stressors (e.g. residential environment, living conditions, lifestyle, use of products for cleaning, cosmetics etc., as well as diet). In addition, house dust, particulate matter or volatile organic compound samples were collected from a subsample.

Combining these two surveys leads to numerous benefits, such as common recruitment of participants, only one procedure of examination and blood sampling, only one procedure of collecting interview data on indicators of health, health behaviour and on exposure pathways, synergies in public relation activities during the fieldwork, combined reputation and awareness of the studies among the public, comprehensive information on living conditions, socio-economic status, behaviour, exposure, health conditions, the chance to combine data on exposure and health and the reduction of costs covered from public resources.

On the other hand, challenges have to be named, such as that the target population and time frame are set by HES (RKI), various agreements are necessary for the cooperating institutes (rights, duties, expenses, data transfer and sharing, publications), detailed arrangements and exchanges are necessary for information materials, questionnaires, ethics and data protection, time schedules must be synchronized, blood resources and questionnaire capacities are limited, trainings, workshops and numerous meetings are necessary and mutual reporting has to be implemented.

² Mauz E et al. New data for action. Data collection for KiGGS Wave 2 has been completed. Journal of Health Monitoring, 2017; 2(S3). DOI 10.17886/RKI-GBE-2017-105. Available at

https://www.rki.de/EN/Content/Health_Monitoring/Health_Reporting/GBEDownloadsJ/ConceptsMethods_en/JoHM_02S3_2017_KiGGS-Wave2_en.pdf%3F_blob%3DpublicationFile

³ Schulz C et al. German Environmental Survey for Children and Adolescents 2014-2017 (GerES V) – the environmental module of KiGGS Waver 2. Journal of Health Monitoring, 2017, 2(S3). DOI 10.17886/RKI-GBE-2017-108. Available at

http://www.rki.de/EN/Content/Health_Monitoring/Health_Reporting/GBEDownloadsJ/ConceptsMethods_en/JoHM_02S3_2017_GerES_en.pdf?_blob=publicationFile

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In KiGGS Wave 2, the participation rate was 41.5 % and in the subsequently performed GerES V 27.7%. Significant differences in age groups or by sex were not detected. Slight differences in the sample composition of the crude net sample of KiGGS Wave 2 and GerES V and administrative population data can be compensated by statistic procedures of weighting. Nevertheless, efforts in arousing interest in participating in health and environmental surveys have to be increased in future studies, especially in low socio-economic status groups.

German Environment Agency

Workshop: Linking HBM and health studies. What are possible opportunities and obstacles?

Experiences from countries which have already combined HBM and health studies: Germany

Antje Gößwald
Robert Koch-Institute (RKI)

Marike Kolossa-Gehring
German Environment Agency (UBA)

Robert Koch Institute Tasks and Aims

- The Robert Koch Institute (RKI) is the government's central scientific institution in the field of biomedicine. It is one of the most important bodies for the safeguarding of public health in Germany.
- Identification, surveillance and prevention of diseases
- Monitoring and analysing long-term public health trends in Germany
- Providing a scientific basis for health-related political decision making
- Informing and advising political decision makers, the scientific sector and the general public
- Executive tasks defined by special laws, in particular with regard to protection from infection, legislation on stem cell research, and attacks using biological agents

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Health Surveys of the RKI and Cooperation with GerES

* Based on the REGULATION (EC) No 1333/2008 OF THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND OF THE COUNCIL of 16 December 2008
Transmission of Data to Eurostat

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Short introduction of KiGGS

Health interview and examination survey for children and adolescents in Germany

Main topics

- health status
- health-related behaviour
- psychosocial risk and protective factors
- health care and living conditions

Examinations

- anthropometrics
- blood pressure
- blood and urine samples
- motor function
- physical fitness and activity

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Exploration of relations

ROBERT KOCH INSTITUT

KiGGS

Studie zur Gesundheit von Kindern und Jugendlichen in Deutschland

"German Health Interview and Examination Survey for Children and Adolescents"

State of health,
Health behaviour,
Socio-economic status,
Living conditions

Umwelt Bundesamt

GerES

Environmental influences

about 2000 pieces of information per child/adolescent!

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The German HBM System: Federal HBM activities in Germany

	German Environmental Survey (GerES)
	German Environmental Specimen Bank (ESB)
	The European Joint Programme HBM4EU: co-operation & harmonisation
 	Co-operation between Ministry of the Environment and Chemical Industry Association
Human Biomonitoring Commission	
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Source of data: (population) representative HBM data

German Environmental Survey (GerES)		Environmental Specimen Bank (ESB)	
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Survey	Period	Age	Size
GerES I	1985 - 1986	25 - 69	2,700
GerES II	1990 - 1992	25 - 69	4,000
		6 - 14	730
GerES III	1997 - 1999	18 - 69	4,800
GerES IV	2003 - 2006	3 - 14	1,790
GerES V	2014 - 2017	3 - 17	2,296

Greifswald (since 1995)
Münster (since 1977)
Halle/S. (since 1995)
Ulm (since 1997)

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Data generated in GerES

Human biomonitoring (HBM)

Analysis of pollutants in human samples
(blood, urine, nasal mucosa, ...)

Co-operation German MoE/Chem. Industry: Global first-time application of new HBM methods in a population study

Drinking water monitoring

Health-relevant chemicals (organic/inorganic)
in domestic drinking water

Indoor monitoring

Pollutants in house dust, suspended particles, and indoor air
investigation of indoor dampness and molds

Interviews and questionnaires

Data on exposure-relevant behaviors and conditions in
Germany,
e.g. drinking water consumption and application of consumer
products at home

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Cooperation agreement

Agreements and arrangements:

- Recruitment of participants
- Blood sampling
- Reporting
- Study data sharing
- Publications
- Expenses

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General aspects for HBM

Benefits of combining HES (RKI) and HBM (UBA):

- **Common recruitment** of participants
- **One procedure** for sampling and examination
- One procedure of **collecting interview data** on indicators of health, health behavior and exposure pathways
- **Synergies in public relation** activities during fieldwork
- **Reputation and awareness** of the studies in the public
- Comprehensive **information** on living conditions, socio-economic status, behaviour, exposure, health conditions (e.g. Anthropometrics, Blood pressure, Spirometry)
- Chance to **combine data** on exposure and health
- **Reduce costs** of public resources

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General aspects for HBM (UBA view)

Challenges of combining HES and HBM

- **Target population** and time frame **is set** by HES (RKI)
- **Various agreements** necessary (rights, duties, expenses, data transfer and sharing, publications)
- **Detailed arrangements** and exchange necessary for information materials, questionnaires, ethics, data protection
- Time schedules must be **synchronized**
- **Limited blood resources** and questionnaire capacities
- Training, workshops, **numerous meetings** necessary
- **Mutual reporting** necessary

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Shared and individual responsibilities

	KiGGS	GerES	Comments
Ethics	x	x	Blood: only RKI
Data protection	x	x	Each institution needs an own
Recruitment	x		Invitation for GerES is provided at KiGGS visit
Address transfer	x		RKI is addressholder
Blood samples	x		Sharing of samples: Ethics allows just 1 prick
Urine samples	(x)	x	RKI: spot urine; GerES: first morning urine
Fieldwork	x	x	GerES 2 months after KiGGS (KiGGS: examination center; GerES: home visit)
Questionnaires	x	x	Have different targets
Laboratory analysis	x	x	Different targets
Public relations and scientific publications	x	x	Together and separately

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Response rate by Age and Sex in KiGGS Wave 2 and GerES V

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Sample Composition by Educational Degree KiGGS W2 and GerES V

KiGGS Wave 2 crude and weighted

KiGGS Wave 2 and GerES V

Human Biomonitoring and HES: tools for protection of health and environment

Human Biomonitoring (HBM):
- examine exposure to chemicals

Health Examination Survey (HES):
- assess health status

- assess the impact on health
- tool to improve chemical policy

Combining environment and health data – some results:

Connection between irritations* and volatile organic compounds (VOC) measured in GerES

* in the last 12 months
C. Schulz, W. Stoff, M. Seiwert, A. Conrad, K. Becker, M. Kolossa-Gehring, S.
ORUP-Tagung, 2009, Stuttgart

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Eye irritations – multi-variate logistic regression analysis

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6.4.2 France

Loïc RAMBAUD from Santé publique France presented French experience on combined HBM and health survey.

In the 2000's, a large cross-sectional survey on the general population was decided to be carried out by the French national program on health and nutrition under the Ministry of Health. In response, the French National Nutrition and Health Survey (ENNS) was set up with the main objective to collect information on the nutritional status of the population.

In the conjunction of this program with the national environmental and health program, and the national program for chronic diseases led to the implementation of ENNS with two secondary objectives: to describe the prevalence of chronic diseases and to evaluate chemical substance exposure of the general population.

During 2006–2007, data were collected among a nationally representative sample of 3,100 adults (18–74 years) and 1,700 children (6–17 years). Harmonized questionnaires were developed for each component; socio-demographic variables, occupation, behavioural exposure and food intake. Clinical examination and biological sample collection were conducted at the same occasion. The clinical examination aimed to describe the prevalence of diabetes, arterial hypertension, metabolic syndrome, dyslipidaemia and associated risk factors. The biological sample collection concerned adults (urine, blood and hair) and children (only hair), and aimed to describe nutritional status and exposure to metals, pesticides and some persistent organic pollutants (POPs).

Following the success of this co-operation in collecting data for different purposes, it was decided by the French Ministry of Health that Santé publique France shall conduct a new national cross-sectional survey, Esteban, to gather information on HBM, health, nutrition, chronic diseases and physical activity of the general population. Esteban included the parameters previously measured in ENNS and was complemented with new parameters, particularly related to the HBM aspect.

Esteban included 2,503 adults (18–74 years) and 1,104 children (6–17 years) residing in metropolitan France, excluding Corsica. The data were collected during a 24-month period in 2014–2016. The survey was divided into three main parts:

- A questionnaire survey, conducted by face-to-face interviews, self-administrated questionnaires and via telephone. In this phase, the consent of participants as well as data on food consumption, physical activity, behavioural exposure characteristics and prevalence of chronic diseases were collected.
- A clinical examination including biological sample collection (urine, blood and hair). Some questions were asked in order to interpret the levels of biomarkers of exposure to chemical agents.
- The creation of a biobank where all biological samples are centralized and stored.

The field study preparation occurred between 2011 and 2014, and fieldwork was conducted between April 2014 and March 2016. Laboratory work, data management and statistical analyses will be performed until the end of 2019. First results on chronic disease prevalence were published in 2018. HBM results will be published in early 2019.

Santé publique France is now working on a follow-up study of Esteban which could occur in the next 5 years.

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COMBINED HBM AND HEALTH STUDIES, EXPERIENCE FROM FRANCE : THE ENNS AND ESTEBAN SURVEYS

Workshop: Linking HBM and health surveys.
What are possibilities and obstacles?

Brussels, June 14th 2018

Loïc Rambaud (loic.rambaud@santepubliquefrance.fr)

PART 1

ENNS THE FRENCH NATIONAL HEALTH AND NUTRITION SURVEY

2006-2007

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THE NATIONAL NUTRITION AND HEALTH SURVEY

- **Started from the *National Nutrition and Health Program* in 2001**
 - Main objective : improve health of the population by acting on nutrition
 - **Need of a national study on general population : ENNS**
 - Inclusion of biological samples collection for biochemical analyses
 - Creation of a biobank

- ***National Environmental Health Program (2004-2008)***
 - Limitation of the impact of the environment on health and claim for a national biomonitoring study
 - **Included as a secondary objective in ENNS**

- ***The National Program for Chronic Diseases***
 - Need to describe prevalence of chronic diseases in France
 - **Included as a secondary objective in ENNS**

3

THE NATIONAL NUTRITION AND HEALTH SURVEY

- **National representative sample of 3,100 adultes (18-74 years old) and 1,700 children (3-17 years old)**

- **Data collection in 2006-2007**
 - **Harmonised questionnaires for socio-demographic, occupation, behavioral exposure, food intakes, etc.**
 - **Clinical exam**
 - Describe prevalence of diabetes, arterial hypertension, metabolic syndrome, dyslipidemia and associated risk factors
 - **Biological samples collection**
 - **Adults** : blood, urine and hair ; **Children** : hair
 - Describe nutritional status of the French population
 - Describe exposure to metals, pesticides and POPs

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PART 2

ESTEBAN STUDY ON HEALTH, ENVIRONMENT, BIOMONITORING, PHYSICAL ACTIVITY AND NUTRITION

2014-2016

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THE ESTEBAN SURVEY

A CROSS-SECTIONNAL STUDY

- **3 parts** : health, biomonitoring, nutrition and physical activities surveys
- Including **2,503 adults** (18-74 years) and **1,104 children** (6-17 years) residing in **Metropolitan France** (excluding Corsica)
- Inclusion over 24 months (**2014-16**) with a growing phase (seasonality of exposure to environmental and food substances)
- Including
 - 1) A « questionnaire survey » (partially conducted face-to-face at home and partially self-administered and via telephone)
 - 2) A « biological and clinical exam » including collection of biological samples (blood, urine and hair)
 - 3) The creation of a biobank

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THE ESTEBAN SURVEY

MAIN OBJECTIVES

- **Estimate the levels of biomarkers of exposure** to chemical agents* present in the environment (incl. food) that have a presumed and/or observed impact on health and to **establish reference values**
- **Describe** food consumptions, physical activity, inactivity and nutritional status
- Estimate the **prevalence of chronic diseases** (diabetes, chronic kidney disease, BPCO, asthma), vascular risk factors (arterial hypertension, dyslipidemias) and non-diagnosed factors in adults
- Estimate **the prevalence of asthma, atopy and allergic diseases in children**

*Metals, Pesticides, Phtalates, Bisphenols, PFCs, PCBs, BFRs, PCDDs, PCDFs

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THE ESTEBAN SURVEY

SECONDARY OBJECTIVES

- Analyse the **determinants of exposure** biomarkers levels, chronic diseases and dietary behavior
- Monitor the **evolution of the indicators** that have already been used in ENNS 2006/2007 and start the monitoring of other fields
- **Compare** with the data gathered from studies conducted abroad
- Dispose of the necessary indicators for **defining and understanding public health policy** monitoring (Public Health regulations, PNNS, obesity plan...)
- **Alert** health authorities in case of emerging phenomena

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STUDY PROCEEDING FOR A PARTICIPANT

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ALL-IN-ONE STUDY : CHRONOLOGY

Field study preparation: 2011 - 2014

- Drafting and validation of protocol
- Publication of tenders
- Obtain regulatory authorisations (CPP, CCTIRS, CNIL, biobank...)
- Develop on-line management tool, training, etc.

Acceptability test: 01/2012 – 04/2012

- 31% acceptance rate for adults and 42% for parents with children

Fieldwork from april 2014 to march 2016

**Environmental and nutritional biomarker dosages centralized:
starting in 2016, ending in 2018**

Statistical analyses in 2018-2019, First results in 2018

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THANK YOU FOR LISTENING

loic.rambaud@santepubliquefrance.fr

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6.4.3 Canada

Kate Werry from the Environmental Health Science and Research Bureau, Health Canada, presented perspectives from combined HBM and health survey activities in Canada.

The Canadian Health Measures Survey (CHMS) is the most comprehensive, direct health measures survey conducted in Canada and is designed to represent the Canadian population. Through personal interviews and the collection of physical measurements, the survey provides baseline data on indicators of environmental exposures, chronic diseases, infectious diseases, fitness, and nutritional status, as well as risk factors and protective characteristics related to these areas. The survey is cross-sectional in design and implemented in consecutive two year cycles.

Since the survey started in 2007, over 270 environmental chemicals have been measured in blood, urine and hair of Canadians. Approximately 90 chemicals are measured in each cycle. Some chemicals such as bisphenol A and mercury are measured in all cycles while others are cycled in and out of the survey depending on current priorities.

Use of the CHMS biomonitoring data is tracked on an ongoing basis and, to date, the data have contributed to or been referenced in over 500 publications. Studies linking health study endpoints with biomonitoring data from the survey have increased in recent years. The majority of these publications have combined urinary and blood data for metals with questionnaire data related to health behaviours (e.g. smoking status, behavioural outcomes), socio-economic information, and environmental factors and exposure (e.g. housing characteristics, pesticide product use). Biomonitoring data have also been combined with some of the physical and laboratory measures including anthropometry (e.g. body mass index) and those related to cardiovascular health and diabetes (e.g. blood glucose, insulin, glycated hemoglobin).

Some of the key advantages to a study such as the CHMS which combines aspects of a health study and a biomonitoring survey include the ability to capitalize on existing infrastructure, reduced costs, access to large data source, opportunities to identify linkages, and the flexibility to address emerging needs. However, where there are advantages, there are also numerous challenges. Prioritization exercises are difficult due to differing priorities of the partner organizations. In addition, due to the ongoing nature of the CHMS and the requirement for content planning to be conducted several years in advance of the survey going out into the field, there isn't always sufficient time for reflection and, at times, the coordination between prioritization of environmental chemicals for human biomonitoring and other health measures can be limited. With regards to the data, while there are many possible uses with such a large data set, underutilization remains to be a challenge and is likely related to the complexity of the analyses and the existing limitations with regards to data access.

Many lessons have been learned over the past 10 years of the CHMS. Strong coordination and alignment between prioritization and planning activities for health measures (direct and questionnaire) and for human biomonitoring is critical to ensuring maximum utility of the data generated in the survey. In order to increase awareness and use of the survey, there are significant benefits to conducting directed outreach. In addition, developing a data analyses strategy can help to identify and conduct priority studies. We have also benefitted from tracking the use of our data to gain a clear understanding of what data are being used, who is using the data, how the data are being used and identify gaps in data usage. Related to these is the need to engage data users (e.g. researchers) early on to help build awareness, increase use and build analytical capacity.

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Perspectives from the Canadian Health Measures Survey

HBM4EU Workshop: Linking HBM and health studies. What are possible opportunities and obstacles?

June 14, 2018

Kate Werry

National Biomonitoring Section

Environmental Health Science and Research Bureau

Health Canada

YOUR HEALTH AND SAFETY... OUR PRIORITY.

Purpose

- (1) Overview of the Canadian Health Measures Survey (CHMS)
- (2) Challenges and advantages to combined human biomonitoring and health measures
- (3) Lessons learned

Canadian Health Measures Survey (CHMS)

Partners:
 Statistics Canada
 Health Canada
 Public Health Agency of Canada

- Nationally representative survey
- Provides information on chronic and infectious disease, physical fitness, nutrition, and other factors that influence health
- Ongoing cross-sectional design carried out in two year cycles
- Survey population aged 3 to 79 years

HEALTH CANADA >

Participant Benefits

- Reimbursement – \$100 provided to cover expenses for participation
- Physical measures data – results provided at end of the clinic visit
- Lab test data – results summary sent 6 to 7 months after the clinic visit (with respondent's prior consent)
- Early reporting protocols are in place for lab results beyond threshold values

HEALTH CANADA >

Participant Burden

- Assessed using various measures including response rates, experiences, trends, observations, Ethics Board submissions

Visit length considerations:

- Typical maximum 1 hour for household questionnaire
- Typical maximum of 2.15-2.5 hours for clinic appointment

	Cycle 1	Cycle 2	Cycle 3	Cycle 4
Household	70%	76%	74%	76%
Questionnaire	88%	91%	88%	91%
MEC	85%	82%	79%	77%
Overall	52%	56%	52%	53%

Survey Content & Planning

- Core**
 - Fixed throughout all cycles
- Theme & Buy-in**
 - Redesigned every other cycle
 - Based upon new initiatives and content ideas
 - Content proposals can be submitted by partners, stakeholders, academics, researchers, etc.
 - Content proposals accepted up to 2.5 years before the start of the survey
 - Questionnaire proposals must have an associated physical or lab measure to maximize the purpose of the CHMS

Additional Considerations for Planning

- Pilot study may be required for complex studies
- Matrix volume limits for laboratory measures
- Operational constraints (e.g. MEC layouts, MEC personnel)
- Approval by Health Canada Research Ethics Board
- Approval by the Canadian Population Health Statistics Program (CPHSP), a governing body with representation from Statistics Canada, Health Canada and the Public Health Agency of Canada

CHMS Components

Household

- Questionnaire
- Sample Collection

Mobile Examination Clinic (MEC)

- Questionnaire
- Sample Collection
- Physical Measures
- Analyses

Laboratory

- Analyses

Biobank

- Sample Storage

Biomonitoring Data Use

HEALTH CANADA >

Combined Biomonitoring and Questionnaire Data Use

	Household				MEC				
	Health behaviour	Socio-economic information	Environmental factors	Health status	Nutrition and food	Medication use	Exposure to air	Health	Medication use
Acrylamide									
Chlorophenols									
Dioxins and Furans									
Flame Retardants	*	*	*	*					
Metals and Trace Elements	*	*	*	*	*				
Nicotine	*								
Organochlorines									
PAHs									
PCBs	o	o		o					
Pesticides: Carbamates									
Pesticides: Organophosphates	*	*	*	*					
Pesticides: Phenoxo Herbicides									
Pesticides: Pyrethroids	*	*	*	*					
Pesticides: Triazine Herbicides									
PFAS									
Plasticizers	*								
Self-Care and Commercial Product Chemicals	*								
Volatile Organic Compounds									
Indoor Air - Volatile Organic Compounds	*	*				*			
Tap Water - Volatile Organic Compounds									

● = published journal article(s)
○ = journal article(s) in progress

Combined Biomonitoring and Health Measures Use

1. Anthropometry

- BMI

2. Lung Function

- 1-second forced expiratory volume (FEV1)
- Forced vital capacity (FVC)

3. Diabetes

- Blood glucose
- Insulin
- Glycated hemoglobin

Advantages to Combined HBM and Health Studies

- Ability to capitalize on existing infrastructure
- Reduced costs
- Access to large data source
- Opportunity to identify linkages
- Flexibility to address emerging needs

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Challenges to Combined HBM and Health Studies

- Differing priorities between partners
- Limited coordination between prioritization of environmental chemicals for human biomonitoring and other health measures
- Lengthy timelines for content planning
- Minimal time for reflection due to ongoing nature of survey
- Underutilization of data set
- Complex analyses
- Limitations with regards to data access and survey awareness

Lessons Learned

- Ensure strong coordination and alignment between prioritization and planning activities for health measures (direct and questionnaire) and for human biomonitoring
- Conduct outreach to increase awareness and use
- Develop data analysis strategy to help identify and conduct priority studies
- Track data use to gain an understanding of what/who/how and identify gaps
- Engage data users (e.g. researchers) from beginning to help build awareness, increase use and build analytical capacity

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For More Information

Health Canada:

canada.ca/biomonitoring

HC.biomonitoring-biosurveillance.SC@canada.ca

Statistics Canada:

search engine: "CHMS" or "CHMS Biobank"

Questions?
kate.werry@canada.ca
or
annie.st-amand@canada.ca

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6.5 Expectations and reservations from countries without combined HBM and health studies

6.5.1 Slovenia

Milena Horvat from Jožef Stefan Institute, Ljubljana, Slovenia, presented the work done on HBM and current status of health surveys in Slovenia.

Based on the legislation for implementation of HBM in Slovenia (Act for Chemicals, No. 110/03), a protocol to start the first national HBM survey was established in 2007. The main trigger to start the national survey was the absence of overall exposure data for chemicals originating from the environment or food intake. Chemicals for the national survey were selected based on the initiatives and recommendations of the World Health Organization (WHO), the International Programme on Chemical Safety and the European Environment and Health Action Plan 2004-2010. The selection criteria for study areas and study population were based on national air and soil monitoring results, toxicological hazard of chemicals, their persistence and bioaccumulation potential, estimated size of exposed populations, analytical capacity, certain public concerns, and trends seen in other countries. Slovenia has three well known heavily polluted areas, 'hot spots', where increased exposure of non-occupationally exposed inhabitants has been previously reported. They include the Upper Mežica Valley in the north, with residual pollution from a closed down lead and zinc (Pb and Zn) mine with a smelting plant; the former mercury (Hg) mine town of Idrija in the west; and the area of the river Krupa (south-west), contaminated with polychlorinated biphenyls (PCBs) from improper disposal of the waste discharge from a former factory of transformers and capacitors. Based on Phase 1, reference values were established for the first time in Slovenia for the studied population.

The second phase of the HBM for EU has just started (2018–2022) and will be aligned with the HBM4EU to secure comparability of the study results. The priority chemicals will include phthalates, DINCH, PFs, BFs, nonil phenols, parabens, triclosan, PBDEs, metals/metalloids (Cd, Pb, Hg, Pb, Mn, Cr), OPs pesticides (in some areas also PCBs and dioxines/furans and additional chemicals such as pyrethroids, glyphosate and PAHs. Ancillary analysis will include creatinine, specific gravity in urine, kidney markers, haemogram, and susceptibility markers (SNPs, single nucleotide polymorphisms).

The first health survey based on EU EHIS (European Health Interview Survey) methodology was implemented in 2004 with 2,118 participants, 68% participation rate and included the population above 15 years of age. In 2014, the second survey was implemented by the National Institute of Public Health (NIJZ). This study included 6,262 participants, with 62% participation and also included population above 15 years of age (<https://podatki.nijz.si/docs/EHIS.pdf>).

In conclusion, Slovenia is one of the rare cases in Europe, where HBM is legally endorsed. Health surveys and HBM are so far implemented separately and are not aligned. In the framework of the HBM4EU, a National HBM Hub was established, which plays an essential role in the future development of joint HBM and health surveys. The institutional arrangements and the use of results in the policy context also remain to be further elaborated.

science and policy
for a healthy future

biomonitoring

Case study: Slovenia

*Expectations and reservations from
countries **without** combined HBM and
health studies*

Milena Horvat

Jožef stefan Institute, Ljubljana, Slovenia

www.biomonitoring.si

Contents

2 Million /
24.000 km²

- **HBM in Slovenia**
 - **Legislative framework**
 - **First HBM survey**
 - **Second (on-going) HBM survey**
- **Health surveys in Slovenia**
- **Conclusions: future perspectives and expectations**

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Legislative basis

ACT on CHEMICALS (O.J. RS No. 16/2008)
CHAPTER IX. PROTECTION OF HUMAN HEALTH AND THE ENVIRONMENT

ARTICLE 49
(protection of people or the environment, prohibitions and restrictions)

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ARTICLE 51.a (biomonitoring of chemicals 1/2)

For the purpose of preparing and monitoring of measures to limit the risk of chemicals to people and the environment, monitoring of presence of chemicals and their breakdown products in people and organisms (hereinafter: biomonitoring) shall be conducted in professionally justified intervals of time.

Biomonitoring is coordinated by the competent authority for chemicals and carried out by health and other public institutes authorised by the Minister, for people and organisms together or separately (hereinafter: biomonitoring performers).

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ARTICLE 51.a (biomonitoring of chemicals 2/2)

Biomonitoring performers shall cooperate with the competent authority for chemicals and among themselves on: preparing a short- and long-term biomonitoring programme, its **intersectoral coordination**, monitoring of its implementation, performing expert evaluation and proposals for measures.

Conditions regarding the **professional and technical competence** of public institutes for performing the biomonitoring from the preceding paragraph shall be set out by the Minister.

Provisions for biomonitoring from this article **do not** infringe upon provisions for biological monitoring **at the workplace** which are governed by regulations on occupational safety and health.

Objectives

Short - term objectives:

- exposure of the inhabitants to chemicals and related health impact throughout Slovenia
- reference (background) values,
- spatial differences in exposure.

Long - term objectives:

- exposure and risk assessments
- Implementation of measures and monitoring of their effectiveness
- science based risk evaluation (awareness building, case-by-case consultations, risk communication ...)
- time trends.

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Phase 1

Pregnant women and men

- Pilot study (2007-2010)
- Full scale(2011-2015)

Phase 2

Additional chemicals in biobanked samples (Phtalates, DINCH, BFs in urine)

- 2018/19

Children and adolescent

- Pilot study (2017-2019)
- Full scale(2018-2021)

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Phase 1. Partners

Funding:

Ministry of Health R Slovenia, National Chemicals Bureau (Lijana Kononenko)

Implementation coordinated by:

Jožef Stefan Institute (Milena Horvat, Darja Mazej, Janja Tratnik Snoj)

In collaboration with

*University Medical Center (Mladen Kersnik, Alenka Briški)
Institut of Public Health Maribor (Slavko Lapanje)*

plus 8 FORMER regional Institutes of Public Health:

Ljubljana, Celje, Nova Gorica, Koper, Murska Sobota, Kranj, Ravne na Koroškem, Novo Mesto (today NIJS)

Methodology

N= 1096 (535 women + 561 men)

● Contaminated site
● Urban area
● Rural area

Contaminated areas;

- past industrial activities: former Hg, Pb mine, former factory of transformers and capacitors related to PCBs pollution
- present industries: smelters, cement factory, power plant and glass factory)

Biomarkers, analytes

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Analysis		
Sample		
Breast milk	Cd, Hg, As, Pb, Se PCBs (28, 52, 101, 138, 153, 180) triglycerides, cholesterol	PCDD, PCDF, dioxin like PCB, PBDE
Blood - women	Hemogram Pb, Cd, Hg, As, Cu, Zn, Se	
Blood - men	Hemogram Pb, Cd, Hg, As, Cu, Zn, Se PCBs (28, 52, 101, 138, 153, 180) triglycerides, cholesterol	PCDD, PCDF, dioxin like PCB, PBDE
Urine	Cd, Hg Markers of kidney function (albumin, alpha-1-mikroglobulin, IgG, NAG) TSH Creatinine	
Hair	Hg	

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Data analyses

- Descriptive statistics, visualization using box plots
- Comparison of levels between subgroups: Analysis of variance
- Determinants of exposure: Multiple linear regression
- adjusting for covariates and cofounders obtained from questionnaires.

Results: Cadmium

↑ women (GM=0.35 µg/L), men (GM=0.23 µg/L)
 ↑ age
 ↑ smoking
 ↑ primary education vs. university level

↑ women (GM=0.26 µg/g crea.), men (GM=0.16)
 ↑ age
 ↑ RURAL AREAS

*no sign. correlation with smoking

Phase 1

Pregnant women and men

- Pilot study (2007-2010)
- Full scale(2011-2015)

Phase 2

Additional chemicals in biobanked samples (Phtalates, DINCH, PFs, BFs in urine)

- 2018/19 (n = 1050)

Children and adolescent

- Pilot study (2017-2019)
- Full scale(2018-2021)

Phase 2 – children (6-9 y) and adolescent (12-15)

- **Pilot study (2017-2019) 300/region**
- Full scale(2018-2021) 100/age group/region

Phase 2 – children and adolescents

- Pilot study (2017-2019) – CRP/V3/1640
- Full scale(2018-2021) - HBM

Priority chemicals: Phthalates, DINCH, PFs, BFs, nonil phenols, parabens, triclosan, PBDEs, metals/metalloids (Cd, Pb, Hg, Pb, Mn, Cr), OPs pesticides (in some areas also PCBs and dioxines/furans)

Additional chemicals: Pyrethroids, Glyphosate, PAHs

Additional analyses: creatinine, specific gravity in urine, kidney markers, hemogram, susceptibility markers (SNPs, single nucleotide polymorphisms)

EHIS – Slovenia

- 2007 – 1st survey based on EU EHIS methodology
 - 2118 participants, 68% participation, population above 15 years of age
- 2014 – 2nd survey - National Institute of Public Health (NIJZ)
 - 6262 participants, 62% participation, population above 15 years of age
 - <https://podatki.nijz.si/docs/EHIS.pdf>

Conclusions (1/2)

- EU COPHES and DEMOCOPHES and **HBM4EU** are timely and relevant for the improvement of national HBM.
- **Recruitment** in HBM remains one of the most challenging part, therefore, **communication** prior/during the study conduct phase play very important role.

Conclusions (2/2)

- The **institutional arrangements** and the use of results in the policy context also remain to be further elaborated.
- **HBM4EU – national commitment and the established National HBM Hub** play an essential role in future development of joint HBM and health surveys.

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Thank you for your attention

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- Field workers and study participants

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6.5.2 Belgium

Greet Schoeters from the Flemish research organization VITO, Belgium, presented Flemish HBM experience and what a more extensive health module would bring to the study.

Flanders is a highly industrialised and densely populated region with a population of 6 million inhabitants. To meet the public concern of environmental pressure and potential health impacts, a prevention decree has been issued in 2004 to set up a network for surveillance of exposure (measured in humans) and/or effects of exposure to physical and chemical factors in the population, with the intention to take measures to protect public health. The decree mentions the development and execution of a program for biomonitoring. Signalling early effects and evaluation of potential associations between exposures and health outcomes were major goals of the programme in addition to surveillance of levels and time trends of environmental chemicals in Flemish citizens⁴.

During the course of the programme, we have developed a framework to recruit a geographically representative sample of mothers and new-borns, adolescents and the elder population. Traditional and well characterized environmental chemicals such as heavy metals, persistent organic pollutants as well as upcoming chemicals that are increasingly used in plastics and consumer products are all included in the programme. In addition, we analysed effect biomarkers and clinical parameters. Health data are collected from registers and from questionnaires (see below):

- Measured effect biomarkers (blood, urine, hair)
 - DNA damage
 - Hormone levels
 - Gene expressions
 - Hair cortisol
 - Serum lipids
- Measured health parameters
 - Weight, height, body fat
 - Blood pressure, exhaled NO
 - NES test: reaction speed, short term memory, sustained attention
- Health data from registers
 - Birth parameters: weight, height, head circumference, APGAR, TSH
 - Clinical examinations at school, tanner stages
- Questionnaires
 - Asthma, allergies (ISAAC)
 - Strengths and difficulties (SDQ)
 - Child behavioural check list
 - Medically assisted pregnancy?

The approach has allowed to link exposure and effect data on the individual level and the results have been reported in many peer reviewed papers (www.milieu-en-gezondheid.be). The approach requires intensive fieldwork, trained field workers, complex procedures for treatment of samples and longer examinations times. Although we have individual data on effect markers, the interpretation of their significance on the individual level is difficult and feedback of the results to participants requires the necessary care and communication skills. Associations between exposures and health outcomes in the cross-sectional study design needs to be interpreted with caution as causality cannot be proven in observational studies. We need confirmation of the results

⁴ Schoeters G, Den Hond E, Colles A, Loots I, Morrens B, Keune H, Bruckers L, Nawrot T, Sioen I, De Coster S, Van Larebeke N, Nelen V, Van de Mierop E, Vrijens J, Croes K, Goeyens K, Baeyens W. Concept of the Flemish human biomonitoring programme. *Int J Hyg Environ Health*. 2012 Feb;215(2):102-8. doi:10.1016/j.ijheh.2011.11.006. PubMed PMID: 22178406.

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in replication cohorts and a longitudinal study design is preferred. Despite these hurdles, the coupling of exposures and effect markers in HBM studies offers new perspectives for studying effects of combined exposures in humans and for the identification of early warning signals which are important tools for better protection of humans against exposures to hazardous chemicals.

Expectations and reservations to combine HBM and health studies- Experience from Flanders

Greet Schoeters
VITO health

FLEMISH POLICY CONTEXT

Art 51 § 1 Flemish Preventiondecree (B.S. 03-02-2004)

1. Can set up a network for surveillance of exposure (measured in humans) and/or effects of exposure to physical and chemical factors in the population, with the intention to take measures to protect public health.
2. Takes at least measures for the development and execution of a program for biomonitoring.
3. Can - in execution of &1 - set up a fund (...). For this purpose a mandatory financial contribution can be imposed on industries or citizens that are responsible for the presence of physical or chemical factors harmful to health.

FLEMISH ENVIRONMENT & HEALTH SURVEY FLEHS

2002-2006

Levels of environmental chemicals in Flemish citizens?
Reference levels? What is normal?
Is the area of residence important?

2007-2011

Reference values for a wider range of pollutants: metals, POPs, pesticides, P
Reference values \longleftrightarrow "hot spots"

2012-2015

Time trends
Exposure and health and socio-economic inequity

2016-2020

Exposure to emerging chemicals: flame retardants, plastic compounds
Healthy behaviours and life style?

Warning system for prevention of adverse health effects

Translation into policy support- participative action plan

FLEHS Reference values

EFFECT PARAMETERS/HEALTH OUTCOMES

- Measured Effect biomarkers (blood, urine, hair):
 - DNA damage
 - Hormone levels
 - Gene expression
 - Hair cortisol
 - Serum lipids
- Measured Health parameters :
 - Weight, height, body fat
 - Blood pressure, exhaled NO
 - NES tests: reaction speed, short term memory, sustained attention
- Health data from registers:
 - Birth parameters: weight, height, head circumference, APGAR, TSH,
 - Clinical examinations at school, tanner stages
- Questionnaires:
 - Asthma, allergy (ISAAC),
 - Strengths and difficulties, (SDQ),
 - Child behaviour check list,
 - Medically assisted pregnancy?
- Exposure related research: air pollutant modelling, dietary POPs intake
- Biomarker development: transcriptomics, epigenetics (cord and saliva)

Newborns (FLEHS I- III)

Health endpoint	Effect measurement	Associated exposure p<0.05
DNA damage	Comet assay Mitochondrial DNA	PFOS ↑, As, Mn
Thyroid hormones	TSH, fT3, fT4 (cord)	Merker PCBs↓, oxychlordan↓
Hormones	SHBG, FSH	Cd↑, PFNA↑, marker PCBs↑, oxychlordan↑ DDE↓, PFOA↑
Birth outcome	Weight length	oxychlordan↓, As, PFOA, PCBs PFOS, PFNA, lindane, oxychlordan, m PCBs↓
Liver	Cholesterol, triglycerides	

↑ Significant increase (p<0.05) in biomarker value associated with increase in exposure P25→P75
 ↓ Significant decrease (p<0.05) in biomarker value associated with increase in exposure P25→P75

Vriens et al, *Int J Hyg Environ Health*. 2017 Apr;220(2 Pt B):468-477. doi: 10.1016/j.ijheh.2017.01.011.
 Remy et al, *PLoS One*. 2014 Mar 24;9(3):e92677. doi: 10.1371/journal.pone.0092677.
 Govarts et al, *Environ Int*. 2018 Jun;115:267-278. doi: 10.1016/j.envint.2018.03.017.

Teenagers 14-15 yrs (FLEHS II, III)

Health endpoint	Effect measurement	Associated exposure p<0.05
Inflammation	Blood cell composition Exhaled NO	oxychlordan
Asthma /allergy	ISAAC questionnaire	PM10, PM2,5, MEP
Cardiovascular	Systolic/diastolic blood pressure	
Neurocognition	NES tests	Blood-Pb, tt-MA, PBDE
DNA damage	Comet assay U-8oxoDG Mitochondrial DNA content	As III, 1OHpyrene, U-Cr, PFOA, PM2,5, As, 1OHpyrene, U-Cr, PM2,5, tt-MA, Cd, Ni, DEHP, AsIII, dioxin-Calux
Hormone levels	TSH, fT3, fT4	Cd, POPs, MEP, Pb, Mn, Cu, TI, PBDE
Puberty development	Tanner stages (boys) Age at menarche (girl)	MEP, pp'-DDE Blood lead

De Croemer et al, *Environ Int*. 2017 May;102:190-199. doi: 10.1016/j.envint.2017.02.014.
 Franken et al, *Int J Hyg Environ Health*. 2017 Apr;220(2 Pt B):468-477. doi: 10.1016/j.ijheh.2017.01.006.
 Franken et al, *Environ Res*. 2017 Jan;152:165-174. doi: 10.1016/j.envres.2016.10.012.
 Kicinski et al, *Environ Res*. 2016 Nov;151:521-527. doi: 10.1016/j.envres.2016.06.035.
 Kicinski et al, *Environ Health*. 2012 Nov 14;11:86. doi: 10.1186/1476-069X-11-86.

Adults 50-65 yrs(FLEHS III)		
Health endpoint	Effect measurement	Associated exposure p<0.05
Metabolic syndrome	Abdominal obesity, triglycerides, HDL cholesterol, blood pressure, fasting blood glucose	Bisphenol A, lindane
Asthma/allergy	Questionnaire	Cr, 2,5-dichlorophenol, diethylalkylphosphate, dialkylphosphate, glyphosate, 2,4,5-T, trans-DCCA ↑ marker PCB's, DDE en DDT ↓
DNA damage	Mitochondrial DNA content	Mercury, PFOS, HCB, oxychlordane ↑ BPA ↓
Kidneyfunction	Serum cystatine ↑ α1-microglobuline ↑	Cd ↑, Ni, 2,5-dichlorophenol, DAP
Neurocognition	NES	mercury, PFNA, oxychlordane, AMPA

PUBERTY DEVELOPMENT

Adolescents: 14-15 yrs

Thyroid hormones (♀ & ♂) and sex hormones (♂)
 Age at menarche (♀) and pubertal stages of Marshall and Tanner (♀ & ♂)

PUBERTY DEVELOPMENT AND CHEMICALS (FLEHS I N= 1679)

Exposure	Effect	Likelihood of adult stage	
GIRLS		Odds (95% CI)	P-value
Blood lead	Pubichair growth	0.65 (0.45-0.93)	0.02
BOYS		Odds (95% CI)	P-value
PCBs	Genital development	3.12 (1.69-5.75)	<0.001
p,p'-DDE	Genital development	3.03 (1.87-4.89)	<0.001
HCB	Genital development	3.12 (1.69-5.75)	<0.001
PCBs	Pubichair growth	2.58 (1.71-3.91)	<0.001
p,p'-DDE	Pubichair growth	1.39 (1.13-1.72)	0.002
HCB	Pubichair growth	3.81 (2.18-6.66)	<0.001
PCBs	Testosterone	+12%*	<0.001

Den Hond et al, *J Expo Sci Environ Epidemiol.* 2011 May-Jun;21(3):224-33. doi: 10.1038/jes.2010.2.
 Croes et al, *Environ Int.* 2014 Oct;71:20-8. doi: 10.1016/j.envint.2014.05.022.

RISK OF MEDICALLY ASSISTED PREGNANCY ASSOCIATED WITH EXPOSURES (N = 1600)

PHTHALATE EXPOSURE AND SG-CORRECTED URINARY 8-OHDG CONCENTRATIONS FLEHS TEENAGERS

Franken et al, *Int J Hyg Environ Health*. 2017 Apr;220(2 Pt B):468-477. doi: 10.1016/j.ijheh.2017.01.006.

CHALLENGES COMBINING : EXPOSURE AND EFFECT

Logistics

- Trained field workers
- Complex field work
- Complex treatment of samples
- Duration of examination

Communication :

- Interpretation of the effect markers at individual level?
- Feed back to participants

- Associations – no proof of causality!
- Statistical power? Confirmation cohorts needed
- Cross sectional studies

OPPORTUNITIES INTRODUCING EFFECT MARKERS TOGETHER WITH EXPOSURE MARKERS

- Effect of Combined exposures (mixtures)
- Early warning biological responses
- Narrow down the physiological variability: restrict age range!

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THANK YOU

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6.5.3 Denmark

Allan Linneberg, from the Center for Clinical Research and Prevention, Bispebjerg and Frederiksberg Hospital, Copenhagen, Denmark, presented existing health surveys in Capital region of Denmark and how HBM module would be incorporated to them.

There is no previous or planned national Human Biomonitoring (HBM) study in Denmark. Also for health surveys, there are no plans to perform National Health Examination Surveys (HESs) but several local/regional HESs have been conducted. Since some of these local/regional HESs are ongoing or longitudinal studies, this would allow inclusion of HBM module to them in theory. There are good opportunities for performing HBM related chemical analysis in Denmark by using biobanks established as part of local HES or as an add-on to planned local HESs.

There is a well-functioning National Health Questionnaire Survey carried out every three to four years. The Danish infrastructure with its nation-wide registries, unique personal identification code and biobanks makes Denmark a favourable setting for HES and HBM. Through register linkage, even cross-sectional studies can form a cohort study as health outcomes can be systematically followed up through administrative registers.

Linking HBM and Health Studies - Expectations and reservations from Denmark

Allan Linneberg, professor, director of research

The Capital Region, Denmark

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The situation in Denmark

- ☞ There is no previous or planned Human Biomonitoring (HBM) studies in Denmark
- ☞ A few earlier research projects have examined specific exposure-disease associations, but not in nationally representative studies
- ☞ There is no planned or recent national Health Examination Survey (HES) in Denmark.
- ☞ One national HES was carried out in 2008-9, but with a very low participation rate: 10%
- ☞ There is a well-functioning National Health Questionnaire Survey

The Danish National Questionnaire-based Health Profile 2017

- ☞ Takes place every 3-4 years
- ☞ Latest survey in 2017
- ☞ 183,000 participants in 2017
- ☞ Participation rate in 2017 was 59%
- ☞ Could be used as a framework for nested sampling for HBM

The Danish National Questionnaire-based Health Profile 2017

Figur 4.1.1 Andel, der ryger dagligt, blandt mænd og kvinder i forskellige aldersgrupper, 2010, 2013 og 2017. Procent

Opportunities for combined HBM/HES in Denmark

- ④ Many local/regional HES performed
 - A few have continuing data collection with opportunity to add-on examinations/procedures
 - mostly funded by research grants
 - Initiated to investigate exposure-disease associations
 - A few are representative for their local area of recruitment
- ④ Many local HES have already established biobanks with biological material (usually accessible without additional costs)
- ④ Unique Danish individual ID-number allows linkage to Danish Health Registries with almost no loss to follow-up

Danish Nation-wide Registries

An example of local HES: the Health2006 concept

- 🔍 Monitor the prevalence and biomarkers of chronic diseases/premorbid conditions and identify novel risk factors/biomarkers
- 🔍 Non-stratified (simple) random sample of 18-69-year-olds living in 10 municipalities the Capital Region of Denmark.
- 🔍 Develop a new concept for the understanding of disease development
 - Cardiorespiratory fitness (lung function, step test)
 - Metabolic fitness (fasting glucose, HbA1C, lipids, liver enzymes)
 - Morphological and muscular fitness (antropometry, hand grip)
 - mental fitness (stress, depression, anxiety, etc.)

Why HES for monitoring disease?

- ☞ Provide valid and up-dated health data for public health decision-makers
- ☞ Data on burden of disease, ... now and in future
- ☞ Need for interventions and monitoring of the effects
- ☞ Questionnaire/interview surveys and registries are insufficient with regard to
 - many chronic diseases e.g. diabetes, chronic obstructive lung disease, asthma, allergic diseases, celiac disease
 - and many pre-morbid conditions, e.g. obesity, hypertension, hypercholesterolaemia, insulin resistance

Niels Henrik Nielsen

Nickel allergy before and after the Nickel Legislation came into force in 1991

Torkil Menné

Jeanne Duus Johansen

Jacob Thyssen

Thyssen, NEJM 2009

Other spin-offs of HES

- ☞ Can be combined with HBM
- ☞ Risk Factor Epidemiology
- ☞ Clinical Epidemiology
 - Reference values (What is normal?)
 - Diagnostic probability/accuracy of tests
 - Prognosis of common diseases
 - Disease mechanisms (clues for drug targets)
 - Changes in diseases or their markers can provide clues of etiology
 - Risk prediction models, e.g. Precard (now Heartscore)
 - Recruitment of participants for clinical trials/research
 - Development and testing of biomarkers

Capital Region of Denmark Research Centre for Prevention and Health

Biobanking

- ☒ Serum/plasma
- ☒ Whole blood
- ☒ Buffy coat
- ☒ Extracted DNA
- ☒ Gene expression (PAX-tubes)
- ☒ Urine
- ☒ Mattress dust
- ☒ Airborne Particles
- ☒ Fecal sample

Criteria for Feasibility Studies – checklist for pilot HBM as part of local HES in the area of Copenhagen, Denmark

- ☒ Eligibility: has experience with organizing HES. Established biobanks available or new collection of biological samples could be add-on in 2019 survey
- ☒ Target population: **One issue is target participation rate of 60%**
- ☒ Biological samples, Health measurements, Questionnaire modules: OK
- ☒ Quality assurance measures: OK
- ☒ Data protection and ethics approval: OK
- ☒ Providing data to IPCheM: OK
- ☒ Funding: Basic infrastructure and operational costs are covered

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Conclusions

- ☞ There is no ongoing HBM in Denmark and no national HES
- ☞ There are good opportunities for performing HBM by using established biobanks or as add-on to planned local HES
- ☞ The Danish infrastructure with nation-wide registries and biobanks makes Denmark a favorable setting for HES and HBM

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6.5.4 UK/England

Jennifer Mindell from the Health and Social Surveys Research Group, Department of Epidemiology & Public Health, UCL, London, UK, presented the long experience of health surveys in England and what should be considered if a HBM module would be added to the Health Survey for England.

Background to the Health Survey for England (HSE)

The Health Survey for England (HSE) is a health examination survey of a random, nationally-representative sample of the non-institutionalised population of England. Each year, from 1991 onwards, a new sample is selected, using a stratified, clustered, approach. Selected households are sent a letter, followed by an interviewer visiting to recruit them, interview those who agree, and measure height and weight. Those who agree then have a nurse visit, who collects further information, takes biophysical measurements, and collects biological samples (which are posted to a central laboratory) from those who agree^{5,6}.

Obstacles

- **Money:** Costs depend on geographical coverage (England/GB/UK); sample size and age-groups; data collection methods; questionnaire length; biological samples & analytes needed; outputs required (data, technical reporting, or substantive reporting); and need for tokens of appreciation.
- **Time:** Longer questionnaire = lower response rates (and more expensive fieldwork and data cleaning costs). HSE allows max 10min additional questions but draft HBM4EU is 50min extra (little overlap).
- **Timing:** Samples collected HSE 2019; HSE data cannot be released before publication (Dec 2020) but analysis and data quality assurance (QA) for HBM4EU needed by 2021.
- **Response rates:** Falling (all surveys in UK and across Europe).
- **Data collection at participants' home:** Blood sample response rates are lower; children need paediatric phlebotomists; difficult in processing samples quickly, limiting bioassays to analytes not affected by sitting at ambient temperature in unspun blood for a day or two OR need to recruit local laboratories and have logistical and funding needs for couriers or nurses' travel time.
- **Identifiability – data protection:** Lack of accessibility to location information to help characterise potential environmental exposures.

Opportunities

- **Marginal not full costs:** Additional modules of (interviewer and) nurse visit, paying only for the additional fieldworker time and other costs.
- **Biological samples taken anyway:** HSE lab is used to sending samples to other laboratories.
- **Much data:** Reduces data collection for HBM (a little); provides richer data for secondary analysis.

Options

- **Stand-alone study:** Most expensive option. Using HSE methods & expertise but not HSE participants.
- **Sub-sample of HSE:** But questionnaire much too long

⁵ Mindell JS, Biddulph J, Hirani V, Stamatakis E, Craig R, Shelton N. Cohort profile: The Health Survey for England. *Int J Epidemiol.* 2012;41:1585-93.

⁶ Fuller E, Prior G, Mindell J (eds.) Health Survey for England. Leeds: NHS Digital; 2017. <https://digital.nhs.uk/pubs/hse2016>

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- **Follow-up study:** Slightly cheaper than stand-alone; good sampling frame; and have data from HSE participation.
- **Age-group:** We do not take blood from children in HSE.

NatCen
Social Research

UCL

Conducting HBM in the Health Survey for England (HSE): Obstacles, Opportunities, and Options

Dr Jennifer Mindell

Professor of Public Health

Health and Social Surveys Research Group

Dept of Epidemiology & Public Health

UCL, London, UK

j.mindell@ucl.ac.uk

 [@j_mindell](https://twitter.com/j_mindell)

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Outline

- Background information on the HSE
- Obstacles
- Opportunities
- Options

Background

- Series of annual health surveys, since 1991
 - 2018 is the 28th HSE
- Authoritative source of health statistics

Commissioned by:

Carried out by:

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Methods: sample design

- Representative of the national general population living in private households in England
- Multi-stage, stratified, random probability sample
- Sampled from Postcode Address File
- Achieved sample:
 - 8,000 adults (16+)
 - 2,000 children (0-15y)

Methods: data collection

- Face-to-face data collection:
 - Higher response rates
 - Interview length
 - Measurements and samples
- Two stages:
 - Interviewer
 - Nurse
- Continuous data collection throughout the year

Methods: fieldwork

1. Advance letter & leaflet sent
2. Interviewer makes contact
3. Interviews conducted
4. Nurse visits conducted
5. Samples posted to laboratory
6. Feedback letters (to participants and GPs)

Conducting HBM within HSE - Obstacles

- Money
- Time
- Timing
- Response rates
- At participants' home
- Identifiability – data protection

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Obstacles - Money

- **Costs of fieldwork depend on:**
 - Geographical coverage (e.g. England/Great Britain/UK)
 - Required sample size and age-groups
 - No. of people per household
 - Achieved for interview or measurements or blood sample?
 - Data collection methods (face-to-face vs self-completion)
 - Questionnaire length
 - Biological samples / analytes required
 - Outputs required (e.g. data/technical reporting/
substantive reporting)

Obstacles – Tokens of Appreciation (TOAs)

- **HSE doesn't use ToAs for specific tasks but NDNS does**
 - e.g. diary completion, urine sample, blood sample
- **If HBM wants to use similar ToAs to NDNS:**
 - might be needed to get reasonable item response
 - would need to fit into overall HSE ToA strategy
 - cannot provide some participants with a blood ToA but not others

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Obstacles - Time

- Longer questionnaires, lower response rates!
- Maximum 10min additional questions per survey
- Draft HBM4EU questionnaire: 50 minutes extra (very little overlap):
 - *Socio-demographic characteristics*
 - Residential environment and home exposures
 - *Dietary habits*
 - *Lifestyle*
 - Occupational exposures & occupational history
 - *Health Status*

Obstacles - Timing

- Samples collected in HSE 2019
- Need analysis & data QA completed by 2021.
- HSE data cannot be released prior to publication (Dec 2020)
 - has impacts on the project timescales.

Obstacles - Response rates

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Obstacles - At participants' home

- **Blood sample response rates lower**
 - Children: Need paediatric phlebotomy expertise
- **Difficulties in processing samples quickly**
 - Only bioassays of substances not affected by sitting in unspun blood at ambient temperature for a day or two
 - Or need to recruit local laboratories + nurses' travel time or couriers

Obstacles – Data protection

- Lack of accessibility to location information to help characterise potential environmental exposure e.g. proximity to landfill site.
 - Is it possible to release the first part of the post code?

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In 1995 the Department of the Environment and the Department of Health collaborated in a small study, which, as it were, piggy-backed on the Health Survey of England, which was intended particularly to examine the relationship between blood lead levels and blood pressure levels in adults not occupationally exposed to lead. This investigation involved scrutinizing PbB levels for 6868 people, 95 per cent of whom were over the age of 16, between January 1995 and February 1996 when their blood was sampled. One hundred and eighty boys and 160 girls aged 11 to 15 were also included, but younger children were not screened. PbB levels above 10 µg/dL were found in 5.3 per cent of the men and 1.2 per cent of the women, while all of the 11–15 year olds had PbB levels below this figure.⁷¹ The data from this recent study suggest that average adult PbB levels declined in the period from 1987 to 1996, but they do not provide any information on the most vulnerable group, namely those aged six and under. These latest British results suggest that average PbB levels have been falling quite rapidly, but they provide no information about the numbers of young children with PbB levels above 10 µg/dL, and there are good reasons for supposing that these have not been falling so rapidly. The reduction in the quantities of lead emitted by motor vehicles must be welcomed, but the problems caused by old paint and water pipes remain to be addressed.

ORIGINAL ARTICLE

Blood lead and blood pressure: evidence from the Health Survey for England 1995

L. Bost¹, P. Primatesta¹, W. Dong¹ and N. Poulter²

¹Department of Epidemiology and Public Health, University College London Medical School, London WC1E 6BT; ²Cardiovascular Studies Unit, Imperial College School of Medicine, St Mary's Campus, London W2 1PG, UK

Objectives: To examine the relationship between blood lead and blood pressure (BP) and to estimate the possible effects of a decrease in blood lead on BP.

Methods: A 2-ml blood sample was collected from a sub-sample of those included in the Health Survey for England 1995, a cross-sectional survey of a nationally representative sample of the adult English population. Blood lead concentration was measured by atomic absorption spectrometry and three BP readings were taken under standardised conditions using the Dinamap 8100 monitor. Analyses were carried out using data on 2563 men and 2763 women aged 16 and over.

Results: In stepwise multiple regression analyses adjusting for various confounders—age, body mass index, smoking status, social class, region of residence

and alcohol intake—blood lead was found to be significantly and positively associated with diastolic BP, and not systolic BP in men, but not in women. These findings were unaffected by the inclusion or exclusion of those on antihypertensive medication, by whether mean or median BP was used in the regression, or by the adjustment for alcohol consumption. A halving of currently prevalent blood lead levels is estimated to be associated with a decrease of between 0.8 to 1.1 mm Hg diastolic BP in men.

Conclusion: These findings in the context of other published data are consistent with a small pressor effect of environmental lead levels on BP. They support recommendations for further efforts to reduce lead in the environment.

Keywords: blood lead; blood pressure; pressor effect

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Opportunities

- Can add additional modules to core HSE
- Marginal costs not full costs for data collection
- Biological samples being taken anyway (adults)
 - HSE lab routinely sends samples to other, specific laboratories
- Much data available on each individual
 - Reduces HBM data collection
 - E.g. demographics, SEP, behaviours, BMI, waist & hip
 - Provides richer data for secondary analysis

Options

- Stand-alone study
 - Using HSE methods & expertise
 - But not HSE participants
- Sub-sample of HSE
 - As part of existing interviewer & nurse visits
 - Which HSE 2019 participants?

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Options

- **Stand-alone study – but most expensive**
 - Using HSE methods & expertise
 - But not HSE participants
- **Sub-sample of HSE – but questionnaire too long**
 - As part of existing interviewer & nurse visits
 - Which HSE 2019 participants?
- **Follow-up study**
 - As additional stage
 - Which HSE 2019 participants?

Follow-up study

- Follow-up would be marginally cheaper than stand-alone survey;
- Benefits include good sampling frame and the fact that HSE data already collected.

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Children?

- Age-groups? 2-19? 4-15? 6-15?
- Much smaller numbers – need entire HSE sample?
- Fewer biological samples collected in HSE, so:
 - Practical difficulties
 - High costs
 - Consent issues
 - Ethical approval
- Concerns re HSE response rates

Taking blood from children

- **Costs** 7x more to collect blood from a participating HSE child (as an extra) than to collect an extra tube from a participating HSE adult.
- **Ability**
 - About 50% of NatCen's nurse panel can/will take blood from 11+.
 - About 15% of the nurse panel can/will take blood from 18 mths +.
- **Response rates**
 - Child blood sample response targets in NDNS are 30% for 1.5-10y and 55% for 11-18y.
 - To get 300 HBM child participants (6-19) would involve the entire HSE sample, once you take RRs into account.

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Options

- Stand-alone study – but most expensive
 - Using HSE methods & expertise
 - But not HSE participants
- Sub-sample of HSE – but questionnaire too long
 - As part of existing interviewer & nurse visits
 - Which HSE 2019 participants?
- **Follow-up study**
 - **As additional stage**
 - **Adults aged 20-45**

<https://digital.nhs.uk/pubs/hse2016>

NHS Digital 70 Years

Data and information Systems and services News and events About NHS Digital

NHS Digital > Health Survey for England, 2016

Publication
Health Survey for England, 2016

This is part of [Health Survey for England](#)

National statistics

Publication Date: 13 Dec 2017

Geographic Coverage: England

Geographical Granularity: Regions

Date Range: 01 Jan 2016 to 31 Dec 2016

[Page contents](#) **Summary**

- [Summary](#)

The Health Survey for England series was designed to monitor trends in

<http://healthsurvey.hscic.gov.uk/>

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Interview: interview core content

Interview	
General health	Smoking
Longstanding illness	Drinking
Hypertension	Physical activity
Diabetes	GHQ-12 / WEMBS / EQ-5D
Social care	Demographic information
Fruit and veg	Measured Height & weight

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Interview: nurse core content

Nurse visit

Prescribed medicines

Vitamins, folic acid

Infant immunisations

- Blood pressure
- Waist and hip circumference
- Saliva sample
- Blood sample (16+)

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6.6 Commonalities and differences between HBM and health studies

6.6.1 Ethics and data protection

Lisbeth E. Knudsen, the leader of Task 11.5 on Ethics, and Berit A. Faber from the University of Copenhagen, Denmark, presented the key issues and procedures related to ethics and data protection in HBM4EU.

Key principles and concepts forming the basis of bioethics and data ethics in relation to approval of study protocols and reporting as well as sample and data sharing within HBM4EU are presented, according to the HBM4EU ethics and data policy document – deliverable D1.5. Major emphasis is on the Rights of the person seen as a data subject where the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) states the definitions, principles, and the means of lawful processing. Emphasis is on the information and the informed consent, which should cover the use of data.

Most projects keep the code with which the identity of the study participants can be linked to survey data for follow-up reasons and clinical contact. This kind of data is characterised as pseudonymised and not anonymised.

Anonymised data are de-identified data impossible to trace back to the person from whom the data originate. In the framework of the HBM4EU, anonymised data means that persons cannot be identified by the researchers who provide the data from different countries. As long as the key to re-identification exists somewhere, the data is not anonymised but pseudonymised.

The GDPR mentions that the regulation does not concern the processing of anonymous information, including for statistical and research purposes:

“The principles of data protection should therefore not apply to anonymous information, namely information which does not relate to an identified or identifiable natural person or to personal data rendered anonymous in such a manner that the data subject is not or no longer identifiable. This Regulation does not therefore concern the processing of such anonymous information, including for statistical or research purposes.”

Recital no. 26 of GDPR states the following on pseudonymisation: *“The principles of data protection should apply to any information concerning an identified or identifiable natural person. Personal data which have undergone pseudonymisation, which could be attributed to a natural person by the use of additional information, should be considered to be information on an identifiable natural person. To determine whether a natural person is identifiable, account should be taken of all the means reasonably likely to be used, such as singling out, either by the controller or by another person to identify the natural person directly or indirectly. To ascertain whether means are reasonably likely to be used to identify the natural person, account should be taken of all objective factors, such as the costs of and the amount of time required for identification, taking into consideration the available technology at the time of the processing and technological developments.”*

Procedures for complying with ethics within HBM4EU are presented as shown in the flowchart developed by Hanna Tolonen and the procedures to be followed related to data transfer agreements and material transfer agreements.

<https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/HTML/?uri=CELEX:32016R0679&from=EN>

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science and policy
for a healthy future

HBM4EU project

Lisbeth E. Knudsen and Berit A. Faber

Ethics and data protection

Session 3, June 15 2018: Workshop:
Linking HBM and health studies

Session 3: Commonalities and differences between
HBM and health studies.

Ethics and data protection
Friday, June 15th, 9.10-9.30

HBM4EU project

Summary

1. Overview

Objectives: To present the key principles and concepts forming the basis of bioethics and dataethics in relation to approval of study protocols and reporting as well as sample and data sharing

2. Strategy

Giving an overview of the ethics- and legal “landscape” – clarifying the principle of lawfulness in bioethics and dataethics

– Providing guidance on HBM4EU procedures

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1. Overview: Bioethics and Data Ethics
2. The International Ethics- and Legal Landscape
3. Bioethics
4. Dataethics
5. HBM4EU Ethics Policy – Approval of Study Protocol

What is ethics?

An academic discipline. Ethics is the critical study of the norms that guide our actions.

Practical skills. Ethics is the practical art of knowing how to apply moral principles in concrete situations

Value systems. Ethics deals with the core values that guide a person or an organisation on the way to its shared vision

- *Ethics is the result of our pursuit to systematically reflect on, analyse, and question the norms and values that guide human action.*
- Göran Hermerén, former President of the European Group on Ethics (EGE)

'Classical ethics'

- **Autonomy** – The right for an individual to make his or her own choice.
- **Beneficence** – The principle of acting with the best interest of the other in mind.
- **Non-maleficence** – The principle that “above all, do no harm,” as stated in the Hippocratic Oath.
- **Justice** – A concept that emphasizes fairness and equality among individuals.

Tom L. Beauchamp and James F. Childress, *Principles of Biomedical Ethics*, 7th ed (New York: Oxford University Press, 2013)

Principles of European research ethics

- •The principle of respect for human dignity
 - •The principle of utility
 - •The principle of precaution
 - •The principle of justice
-
- A moral principle is a general guide of action that provides a standard of relevance or “reasonableness”
 - A moral principle is applied *prima facie*, i. e. it must be observed unless it comes in conflict with any other, equally pertinent, consideration.

HBM4EU Linking HBM and Health studies June 14-15
Brussels 2018

1. Principles for information, invitation and informed consent

The research participant: 2 areas of protection:

1. A human individual participating in **biomedical research**
2. A human individual participating in research involving **health data/biomonitring data** concerning the person

Bioethics:

**World Medical Association
(WMA): Helsinki declaration**

Bioethics convention

Data ethics:

**General Data Protection
Regulation (GDPR)**

HBM4EU Linking HBM and Health studies June 14-15
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2. Information and invitation

Requirements for information about the project - examples of important issues:

HBM4EU Ethics Policy:

The merging of Bioethics and Dataethics principles

The principle of easily understandable language

(Bioethics Convention) and (GDPR) targeted to the age and maturity of the group of prospect participants.

Rights of the person seen as a research participant:

What is the project about?

What are the implications of participating?

Who is leading the project?

Who has financed the project?

Reflection time before agreeing to participation

Possibility of withdrawal from the project

Incidental findings policy

Secondary research, Data sharing and data transfer

HBM4EU Linking HBM and Health studies June 14-15
Brussels 2018

Information and invitation

Rights of the Person seen as a *data subject*

GDPR: states the definitions, principles, and the means of lawful processing

Article 4: Definitions

Article 5: Principles

Article 6: Means of lawful processing

HBM4EU Linking HBM and Health studies June 14-15
Brussels 2018

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Bioethics

Anonymised

Anonymised data are deidentified data impossible to trace back to the person, from where the data originate. In the framework of the HBM4EU anonymised data means, that persons cannot be identified by the researchers providing the data in the different countries. As long as the key to reidentification exists somewhere, the data is not anonymised, but pseudonymized.

The GDPR mentions that the regulation does not concern the processing of such anonymous information, including for statistical and research purposes:

“The principles of data protection should therefore not apply to anonymous information, namely information which does not relate to an identified or identifiable natural person or to personal data rendered anonymous in such a manner that the data subject is not or no longer identifiable. This Regulation does not therefore concern the processing of such anonymous information, including for statistical or research purposes.”

Link to GDPR:

<https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/HTML/?uri=CELEX:32016R0679&from=EN>

Bioethics

Pseudonymised

The GDPR introduces the concept of pseudonymisation as a tool for enhancing security by design. The GDPR defines pseudonymisation as:

“The processing of personal data in such a way that the data can no longer be attributed to a specific data subject without the use of additional information.” To pseudonymise a data set, the “additional information” must be “kept separately and subject to technical and organizational measures to ensure non-attribution to an identified or identifiable person.” Pseudonymisation is thus seen by the GDPR as a privacy-enhancing technique where directly identified data is held separately and securely from processed data in order to secure non-attribution. The GDPR sets new standards for Data protection by design and accountability. Organisations are required to adopt significant new technical and organisational measures to demonstrate their GDPR compliance.

Link to GDPR:

<https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/HTML/?uri=CELEX:32016R0679&from=EN>

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Bioethics

Pseudonymised

Recital no. 26 states the following on pseudonymisation:

“ The principles of data protection should apply to any information concerning an identified or identifiable natural person. Personal data which have undergone pseudonymisation, which could be attributed to a natural person by the use of additional information should be considered to be information on an identifiable natural person. To determine whether a natural person is identifiable, account should be taken of all the means reasonably likely to be used, such as singling out, either by the controller or by another person to identify the natural person directly or indirectly. To ascertain whether means are reasonably likely to be used to identify the natural person, account should be taken of all objective factors, such as the costs of and the amount of time required for identification, taking into consideration the available technology at the time of the processing and technological developments.”

Link to GDPR:

<https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/HTML/?uri=CELEX:32016R0679&from=EN>

4. Dataethics: Principles

Handling of data derived from biological samples and questionnaires

Wet data: Biological samples

Dry data: Digital data derived from biological samples and other data

General Data protection regulation:

Definitions Article 4

Principles Article 5

Link to GDPR:

<https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/HTML/?uri=CELEX:32016R0679&from=EN>

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4 Dataethics and GDPR - Principles

GDPR Article 5: Principles

Data should be processed lawfully, fairly and in a transparent manner in relation to the data subject ('lawfulness, fairness and transparency');

GDPR Article 6: Lawfulness of processing

4. Dataethics - Datalaw Lawfulness of processing

GDPR Article 6 Excerpt

1. Processing shall be lawful only if and to the extent that at least one of the following applies:

(a) the data subject has given consent to the processing of his or her personal data for one or more specific purposes;

(b) processing is necessary for the performance of a contract to which the data subject is party or in order to take steps at the request of the data subject prior to entering into a contract;

(c) processing is necessary for compliance with a legal obligation to which the controller is subject;

(d) processing is necessary in order to protect the vital interests of the data subject or of another natural person;

(e) processing is necessary for the performance of a task carried out in the public interest or in the exercise of official authority vested in the controller;

(f) processing is necessary for the purposes of the legitimate interests pursued by the controller or by a third party, except where such interests are overridden by the interests or fundamental rights and freedoms of the data subject which require protection of personal data, in particular where the data subject is a child.

HBM4EU Ethics Policy: Ethics and approval of study protocol What is required and how to arrange it

Lawfulness and HBM4EU

1. *Compliance with the requirements of HBM4EU Ethics Policy – which will take into account:*
2. *Compliance with EU- and other international ethics and legal framework:*
3. *Bioethics: WMA: Declaration of Helsinki,*
4. *Council of Europe: Bioethics Convention, EU: Charter of Fundamental rights Childrens' rights, Occupational Research participants' rights.*
5. *Dataethics: EU: General Data Protection Regulation*

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HBM4EU project

Recruiting Research Participants

Information, Invitation, Informed Consent Form

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Procedure

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Information Leaflet

Template p1-2

You have been randomly selected [explain how the selection took place, eg. register] to represent [describe the study population in easy to understand terms, eg. your country], if recruiting through an intermediary organization. The [relevant organization] has consented to participate in the study and has agreed to allow the HBM4EU researchers to extend an invitation to you to participate if you decide to do so. Representativeness and usefulness of the results of the study will depend on people we contact to get involved.

How will the study be carried out?

The study will take [specify time period] in [your country] and [number] other European countries. It will include a total of [number] participants and [number] of them will come from [your country]. Each participant will provide biological samples and will complete a questionnaire. We will analyze this information to determine your exposure to a variety of potentially harmful environmental chemicals.

What do I have to do if I agree to take part?

If you agree to participate, please complete and return the enclosed green reply card ("I want to participate") within XX days from its receipt.

OPTION 1: ANONYMOUS orange card, with non-responder questionnaire replies (i.e. no GDPR requirements)

If you do not want to participate, you can help us improve future studies by returning the orange reply card within XX days from its receipt. By answering a few optional questions completely anonymously, you can help us to understand how the people who choose not to take part in the study compare to the people who want to take part.

OPTION 2: EPONIMOUS orange card, with non-responder questionnaire replies (i.e. GDPR requirements apply)

If you do not want to participate, please complete and return the orange reply card, which contains some optional questions to help us improve future studies. Your information will be kept private and confidential and will be used only according to your consent.

What happens after you receive my reply card? [needs to be adjusted according to the national study plan]

- On receiving your green "yes" card, we will confirm if you are eligible to participate in the study. This study will include volunteers that must meet the following requirements: **consent** and we can only include participants that fulfil them, up to a maximum of 400 individuals.
- If you do not fulfil the eligibility requirements or the maximum participation limit of this study has been reached by the time when we received your green card, you will receive a letter about it. You may also be asked whether you wish to be contacted by your national study coordinator for participation in future HBM4EU studies.
- If your participation is confirmed, we will contact you to agree on a suitable date for your appointment with our research team at [OPTION A: our Examination Centre (specify location) and your travel costs will be covered by us / OPTION B: your home].
- You will be asked to confirm your willingness to participate in the study by completing and signing the enclosed consent form in duplicate. You will keep one copy for your records and

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Information Leaflet

Template p3-4

we will keep the other for our records. You could ask any questions you wish and request adequate time to clarify your concerns prior to signing.

- Prior to the appointment, you will receive a pre-visit letter providing you with notice of any preparations required before the appointment. You may also receive a reminder message via phone / SMS / post, if you wish.

How do I prepare for the visit?

No special preparation is necessary. If any preparation is required, you will be informed beforehand.

What will happen during our appointment?

[On arrival at the Examination Centre a member of our team will be available to answer any questions you may have / A member of our research team will visit you at home.] You will have time to ask any questions you may have and receive answers.

If you have not already completed and signed a consent form prior to the appointment, you must do so at this point.

A code will be assigned by the study coordinator, who will then remove all personal identifiable information to protect your privacy and make it impossible to track data or samples back to you. The researcher will take your [specify biological samples].

We will ask you to complete a questionnaire to collect information about your personal data, living conditions, food intake, your workplace and your possible contact with chemicals.

The visit will last no longer than [XX minutes]. **Only if the appointment takes place in an examination centre, you will be given a fixed payment to cover your travel expenses.**

What will happen to my samples, data and results?

Your samples will be used only according to your informed consent. The results of the study will not be traceable back to you or any other participant.

We will transfer your coded samples to specialized laboratories for analysis [specify where the analysis will be conducted for each country]. Your samples will be examined to measure your exposure to [specify which chemical contaminants will be analyzed and why]. Your samples will then be stored at [specify place and length of storage] for possible use in future ethically approved studies of chemical exposure. Coded data collected from you and other participants will be stored and used for research purposes and may be combined with other data from different sources.

The results of the study will be provided to national and European authorities to support policy actions related to chemical management for public health protection. They will also be disseminated to other stakeholders, including the general public, scientists and other interested parties. The sharing of data will be facilitated through dedicated data infrastructures and/or information systems (e.g. through IPoEM, which is the European Commission information platform for Chemical Monitoring).

How can I learn about the results of the study?

When the study is completed [specify according to study plan in approximately XX weeks/months], you will be informed by [XXX] about your personal results [or specify], unless you expressed a wish not to receive them on your certificate of informed consent.

¹ <https://ipodem.jrc.ec.europa.eu/>

In the event that high levels of chemicals are detected, you will be advised to review your results with your family / personal doctor.

You will also be informed about the collective results of the study. These will be published as a study report and will be openly accessed at <https://www.hbm4eu.eu/>.

How will my privacy be protected?

HBM4EU complies with the European Data Protection Regulation (EU) 2016/679. Your name will be replaced by a code and all electronic and paper records will be blocked from unauthorized access to protect your private information. Published reports of the study will not contain information that can trace back to you. Third parties will not have access to your personal results, unless you consent to.

Why do you need my written consent?

Your written consent confirms that you volunteer to take part in the study after understanding what is required from you and what your rights are. You have the right to withdraw your participation without any consequence at any point (including any data or samples already provided, if they have not been completely anonymized and so impossible to be traced back to you) and the right to choose if you want to receive your individual results or not. You will also confirm that we can contact you in the future to tell you about your personal results or for historical, statistical or scientific purposes. A copy of the Certificate of Informed Consent, which you will be asked to complete and sign before taking part in the study, is attached to this leaflet and you can keep it for future reference.

How will I benefit if I participate?

- You will have the opportunity to receive a specialized medical briefing, which is not typically available during your routine medical assessment. However, please note that this examination is only complementary to and not a substitute for your regular health care checks.
- You will receive information regarding your exposure to specific chemicals and the associated potential health impact.
- You will have the right to receive your personal results [if you wish] [to how any new high incidence of chemical levels should be reported], which you may subsequently further examine with your doctor.
- You will learn about selected chemicals, their possible effect on health and ways to avoid exposure.
- [Describe any other incentives, if applicable]
- You and all people like you in [your country] and in Europe will benefit from the collective results of the study, which will be used to [understand the exposures of people to harmful chemicals and how these can affect the human body / develop harmonized / new methods to measure exposures / develop better chemical management policies across Europe]

Are there any risks if I join the HBM4EU study?

Some participants may experience minor discomfort during the collection of [blood] samples. All sampling will be conducted by qualified and specially trained health professionals. [If applicable: study participants will be covered by insurance for any adverse events relevant to their participation without any charge]

Are there any costs to me?

No, the study will be conducted at no cost to you. Participation is voluntary, without reimbursement. [If applicable] Travel and out of pocket expenses can be claimed back through [specify how]

What if I have any concerns or complaints while I'm taking part in the study?

Information Leaflet

Template p5

Your wellbeing is our foremost priority and we will take all necessary precautions to ensure your comfort and safety. If you have any concerns during your appointment, please discuss them with our research team or at any time by contacting the study leader ([Title, Name, Tel: [xxxxxxx], Email [xxxxxxx]). You have the right to opt out of the study at any time. In the unlikely event that want to file a complaint about the study, you may do so by contacting [Title, Name, Tel: [xxxxxxx], Email [xxxxxxx], who is not formally connected to the study and serves as an independent overseer of its implementation.

How can I quit the study?

You are free to withdraw from the study at any time, without any consequences by [sending an e-mail to / calling XXX]. We will ask you to confirm your wishes by signing the attached withdrawal form. On this form you can indicate one of the following options:

- "No further contact but samples and data can be used".
We will no longer contact you, but have your permission to retain and use information and samples that you have already provided.
- "No further contact and my samples and data cannot be used".
We will no longer contact you and will destroy your samples and data, unless they have been completely anonymized and we cannot trace them back to you. We will retain your signed consent and withdrawal forms as a record of your wishes and for audit purposes.

You can request a copy of this form from us using the contact details provided below.

Who do I contact if I'm unsure about anything or would like further information about the study?

You can contact us on [name, phone number, email] for any further clarifications or visit <https://www.hbm4eu.eu/>.

Thank you for your time and consideration!

Informed consent template

Draft

SCIENCE AND POLICY FOR A HEALTHY FUTURE

GOVERNMENT / INSTITUTE LOGO

CERTIFICATE OF INFORMED CONSENT

Study description

Title: _____ Study Code: GS/NA/YY
Participant Code: XXXXXXXX

Researcher identifier

Researcher Name: _____ Telephone: _____
Department: _____ Email: _____
Institution: _____
Address: _____

I, the undersigned, hereby confirm the following:

1	I understand that my participation is voluntary in the research as defined in the "Study description" and that I am free to withdraw at any time without giving any reason, without our medical care or legal rights being affected, by following the steps explained in the attached information leaflet	Initials
2	a) I have been given the "Information for Participants" leaflet, which explains what my participation involves, including my rights (to be forgotten, to withdraw and remove any data/samples provided, to choose whether I wish to be informed of my personal results) and commitments relevant to the research study. b) I have had the opportunity and time (at least 24 hours) to consider and comprehend the information in the "Information for Participants" leaflet, which provided me a comprehensive understanding on the research plan of the study. c) I have had the opportunity to ask questions and I received satisfactory answers. d) I am aware that in case I withdraw my current consent, my data will be used only for the purpose of the research to be continued.	
3	I consent to a long-term (if specify duration) storage and use of my specify type samples and personal data collected in this study for OPTION A: OCCUPATIONAL STUDIES the assessment of my occupational exposure to H2 and its potential health impact / or OPTION B: DOMESTIC HOUSEHOLD STUDIES public and environment health-related research purposes, even in the event of my death or being made incapacitated	
4	I consent that the specify organization, represented by specify position in Organization of principal investigator will have the exclusive access to my personal information and will encode my data and samples with a method - according to the currently available safeguards - so that other users of my data cannot trace back to the specifying the/or individual track	
5	I consent that my coded samples and/or data can be transferred to specialized laboratories, institutes, databases, data infrastructures, research establishments, administrative authorities and institutions in the European Union and associated countries or used for public announcements and reports within the scope of the study.	
6	I consent that the specify organization, represented by specify name and full contact details of principal investigator may contact me in the future for public	

and environment health-related research purposes.

2) I understand that I will not benefit financially from taking part in this study

3) I understand that I have the right to receive my personal results as stated in the information leaflet and I indicate my preference as follows:
Please mark one option only.
 I wish to receive my personal results
 I wish to receive my personal results only if they exceed the health-based guidance values used in the study
 I do not wish to receive my personal results

To be completed if the participant is unable to provide signature:
I have witnessed the accurate reading of the consent form to the potential participant, and the individual has had the opportunity to ask questions. I confirm that the individual has given consent freely.

Thumb print of participant

Name of person taking consent: _____ Signature of person taking consent: _____ Date: _____

Statement by the researcher/person taking consent
I have read out the information leaflet and consent form to the potential participant, and to the best of my ability I have made sure that they understand that the following will be done:
1.
2.
3.
4.
I confirm that they were given an opportunity to ask questions about the study, and all the questions asked have been answered truthfully and to the best of my ability. I confirm that the individuals have not been coerced into giving consent, and that consent has been given freely and voluntarily without any objection raised.
A copy of this Informed Consent has been provided to the participant.

Print Name of Researcher / person taking the consent: _____ Signature of Researcher / person taking the consent: _____ Date: _____

AD-CP V318

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Data Transfer

Form to be used

HBM4EU Data Transfer Form	
Purpose of the form and signatures	P. 1

Version Number of the HBM4EU Data Transfer Form: 2

Release Date: 15/12/2017

1) Purpose of this form:

The data transfer documentation is to be completed by Data Owners/Data Providers. In case a Data Provider is assigned by the Data Owner, the Data Provider will be responsible for implementation of the procedures described in the HBM4EU data management plan and data policy.

Using this form, Data Owners/Data Providers indicate under which conditions the data to which this agreement applies (Part A) are transferred to the HBM4EU repository (Part B) and integrated into IPCHEM (Part C). The metadata shall be made openly available via IPCHEM as minimal requirement.

2) Signatures:

Signing this form the Data Owner/Data Provider:

- 1) agrees to make the data collection(s) (specified in Part A of this form).

Material transfer

Draft

		Form: Material Transfer Record Form Valid since: Mar 2018 Version: V 0.1	
---	--	--	--

Material Transfer Record Form Page 1 of 2

Provider

Name of the institution: _____
 Address: _____
 Postal code: _____
 Country: _____
 Person in charge: _____

Recipient

Name of the institution: _____
 Address: _____
 Postal code: _____
 Country: _____
 Person in charge: _____

The MATERIAL(S) described below is/are supplied by PROVIDER to the RECIPIENT subject to the terms and conditions of the HBM4EU MTA, and the HBM4EU Data Policy, which control in the event of any discrepancy between the language here and there.

Description of the MATERIAL(S) Briefly describe the MATERIAL(S) being transferred (quantity, type of material) under the HBM4EU MTA. Detailed information including the unique identifier (barcode) of each sample will be provided by the Provider with each shipment in the data transfer template form. Add additional pages if required.

Description of the agreed use of the MATERIAL(S) including the termination of this agreement. Add additional pages if required.

State the estimated end date for using the biological materials according to this agreement:

State when the analysis is planned to be finished (year, month): _____

Samples will be:

Completely consumed during analysis.
 Destroyed after analysis. Estimate date for destruction of samples (year, month): _____
 Returned after analysis. Estimate date for return of samples (year, month): _____

Other: _____

Page 2 of 2

		Form: Material Transfer Record Form Valid since: Mar 2018 Version: V 0.1	
---	--	--	--

The use, transfer, allocation of ownership/ownership of Materials, Data and HBM4EU results that arise from use of the Materials shall be consistent with the HBM4EU objectives and intentions. Specific terms and conditions are set forth below.

MATERIAL(S) are to be used for the Agreed use as stated above only. MATERIAL(S) shall not be transferred by the RECIPIENT to any other party either within or outside HBM4EU without written permission of the PROVIDER. The PROVIDER retains ownership of the MATERIAL(S). Access to the MATERIAL(S) is granted to the RECIPIENT for the purpose of carrying out the Agreed use for the period required to complete the Agreed use or until termination of the HBM4EU MTA, whichever is earlier. No other license to the Materials, implied or otherwise, is granted. The Data can be transferred and used according to the HBM4EU Data Policy.

[Optional clause] Any dispute or controversy arising in connection with the transfer of MATERIAL(S) documented herewith which is not resolved by the designated officers of the PROVIDER and RECIPIENT in accordance with the HBM4EU MTA shall be finally settled in accordance with the following terms:

Describe the controlling law and any dispute mechanism (in the event that this is not the controlling law will be the jurisdiction in which the HBM4EU member institution is located. Add additional pages if required).

The PROVIDER and RECIPIENT, by their duly authorized representatives, hereby accept all terms and conditions reported stated in the HBM4EU MTA including its further applicable documents.

Provider **Recipient**

Date: _____ Date: _____

Signature: _____ Signature: _____

Duplicate originals of this form shall be fully completed and executed and exchanged, with copies sent electronically via facsimile transmission, pdf attachment to e-mail, or the fax) within three days to the Ethics Board (Susanne E. Knudsen, University of Copenhagen, Faculty of Health Sciences, Department of Public Health, Øster Farimagsgade 5A, room 5.2.11, DK-2301 Copenhagen, Denmark, Phone: +45 35227015, E Mail: eth@hbm4eu.dk) or to such other e-mail address as may be provided by the management board of HBM4EU in the future.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101019710.

Info Email: HBM4EU@hbm4eu.dk
 Developed by BMF, ÅL, NCH, IS

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HBM4EU Ethics Policy Ethics and approval of study protocol: How to arrange it

1. Check your National system for ethics approval of research projects
2. Check your National system – Does your National System require approval both for the bioethics-part of the research project and for the dataethics-part of the project?
3. Biological samples: Check if your National system requires special approval for collecting, storing, handling and sharing of biological samples and data derived from these.

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Template

Submission of documents related to research ethics and data/material transfer

Version 2018-28-05

Name of the study	In national language	
	In English	
	Used acronym	
	Country	Country ?
Owner of the study	Institute	
	Contact person(s) name(s) and e-mail address(es)	
	Partner in HBM4EU	Partners ?
	For LTP, the beneficiary	Beneficiary ?

Please note: The filename should be descriptive of the contents and should include as prefix "InstituteAcronym_StudyAcronym_". For the different document types a different suffix: "InformedConsent", "InformationLeaflet", "EthicalApproval", ... or whatever is relevant as naming (e.g. USA_ESB_InformedConsent). Avoid that the documents are named in national languages.
We emphasize to please use the same acronym for institute and study when filling out all other documentation regarding their data collection (such as the metadata fiche, data transfer agreement, material transfer agreement, ...).

Informed consent	Copy of the informed consent(s) and related information material in national language	Drop down	Comments: file name:
	Copy of the informed consent(s) and related information material in English, if available	Drop down	file name:

Template

Submission of documents related to research ethics and data/material transfer

Version 2018-28-05

Name of the study	In national language	
	In English	
	Used acronym	
	Country	Country ?
Owner of the study	Institute	
	Contact person(s) name(s) and e-mail address(es)	
	Partner in HBM4EU	Partners ?
	For LTP, the beneficiary	Beneficiary ?

Please note: The filename should be descriptive of the contents and should include as prefix "InstituteAcronym_StudyAcronym_". For the different document types a different suffix: "InformedConsent", "InformationLeaflet", "EthicalApproval", ... or whatever is relevant as naming (e.g. USA_ESB_InformedConsent). Avoid that the documents are named in national languages.
We emphasize to please use the same acronym for institute and study when filling out all other documentation regarding their data collection (such as the metadata fiche, data transfer agreement, material transfer agreement, ...).

Informed consent	Copy of the informed consent(s) and related information material in national language	Drop down	Comments: file name:
	Copy of the informed consent(s) and related information material in English, if available	Drop down	file name:

Template

Page 2

		Comments
Ethical approval	Copy of the ethical approval in national language	Drop-down
	Copy of the ethical approval in English, if available	Drop-down
	If English version not available, provides a short summary of the contents	Free text field
	Is secondary use of data/samples in HBM4EU allowed?	Drop-down
	Name of the body/bodies issuing the ethical approval	Free text field
	Date of approval	Free text field
	Expiration date for approval	Free text field
Data protection	Copy of the data protection approval in national language	Drop-down
	Copy of the data protection approval in English, if available	Drop-down
	If English version not available, provides a short summary of the contents	Free text field
	Can aggregated data be transferred to HBM4EU repository?	Drop-down
	Can single measurement data be transferred to HBM4EU registers?	Drop-down
	Can aggregated data be transferred to HBM4EU repository?	Drop-down
	Name of the body/bodies issuing the data protection approval	Free text field
Date of approval	Date	
Expiration date for approval	Date	

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Template

Page 3

Biobank	Copy of the biobank approval in national language	Drop-down
	Copy of the biobank approval in English, if available	Drop-down
	If English version not available, provides a short summary of the contents	Free text field
	Is secondary use of data/samples for HBM4EU allowed?	Drop-down
	Name of the body/bodies providing approval	Free text field
	Date of approval	Date
	Expiration date for the approval	Date
Renewal of the approval(s) is required before use in which documents require renewal?	Drop-down	
	Approval ?	

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Template

Page 4

		Comments
<p>According to the documentation provided, the following operations can be considered, after consultation of the data controller</p>	Use of single measurement data for specific HBM4EU objectives	Drop down
	Use of single measurement data for all HBM4EU research	Drop down
	Use of single measurement data without purpose limitation	Drop down
	Use of aggregated data for specific HBM4EU objectives	Drop down
	Use of aggregated data for all HBM4EU research	Drop down
	Use of aggregated data without purpose limitation	Drop down
<p>Information on planned data use</p>	To be used by WP	WP?
	To be used in Task	Task?
	The work will start	Calendar
<p>Information on planned material use</p>	To be used by WP	WP?
	To be used in Task	Task 1-4
	The work will start	Calendar
		Other WP / tasks:

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Template

Page 5

		Comments
<p>Information on planned data use</p>	Copy of the datatransfer agreement - name of file dates	Drop down
	Copy of the material transfer agreement - name of file dates	Drop down
		File name:
		File name:

<p>Local ethics expert</p>	Name	
	E-mail address	
	Telephone number	
	Date	Calendar
<p>Data Controller</p>	Name	
	E-mail address	
	Telephone number	
	Date	Calendar
<p>Person filling in this form</p>	Name and capacity (data controller or processor)	
	E-mail address	
	Telephone number	
	Date	Calendar
	Date when received by the leader of Task 3.5	Calendar

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5. HBM4EU Ethics Policy – Approval of Study Protocol

HBM4EU

Special requirements for approval of study protocol

Old projects

Ethics templates

Special requirements for approval of study protocol – new projects (Recommendations of WP7, Special requirements for data transfer WP 10)

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Brussels 2018

Contacts

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Berit Andersen Feber, LLM, Research Assistant
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Faculty of Health and Medical Sciences, Dept of Public Health, Environmental Epidemiology Group

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Speaker's information

Lisbeth E. Krudsen, MD, PhD professor in animal toxicology has worked with ethics and HBM since 2007 in designing, performing and reporting field studies. Appointed scientific member of the National ethics committee, the chair of the institutional ethics committee. Leader of Task 1.5 in HBM4EU: Ethics and data protection and partner in the Task 2.5 Training, National Hub contact point of Denmark

Speaker's information

Berit A. Feber, LLM works as a research assistant at Faculty of Health and Medical Sciences, Environmental Epidemiology Group, Copenhagen University, Denmark. Has worked in the Danish Ministry of Health, the Danish Council of Ethics and the Danish National Commission on Health Research Ethics.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 733032.

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6.6.2 Sampling and recruitment

Hanna Tolonen from the National Institute for Health and Welfare (THL), Finland, presented issues related to sampling and recruitment of participants on HBM and health studies.

In both HBM and health studies target population can be defined in many ways depending on the aim of the specific study. When monitoring at the population level is the main aim of the study, general population is often defined as a target group. Covered age group varies between studies. In health surveys, usually no specific exclusion criteria are used, but in HBM studies some exclusion criteria may be needed depending on substances of interest.

To obtain representative sample, as good sampling frame as possible should be used. The availability and possibility to use different types of sampling frames vary between countries. Many countries have population registers which are updated regularly but in some countries other types of list such as census, list of patients, students etc. have to be used.

Health surveys usually require relatively large sample size to be able to provide nationally representative information by sex and age groups. EHES recommendation is for example 4,000 persons per country. For HBM studies, significantly smaller sample sizes are often used (500 persons per country). This means that it is much easier to incorporate a HBM module to a national health survey than the other way around.

For representative results, as high participation rate as possible is required to avoid non-response bias on the results. There is a lot of evidence that for example questionnaire design, timing and length of the survey visit, incentives and access to the survey examination site can effect on obtain participation rates. Key message being that try to minimize the participants burden to maximize participation rate.

HBM4EU

science and policy
for a healthy future

Sampling and recruitment

Hanna Tolonen
National Institute for Health and
Welfare (THL), Finland

Workshop on linking HBM and health studies,
14-15 June 2019, Brussels, Belgium

Twitter: @HBM4EU, #HBM_HES,
@tolonen_hanna

Target population

HBM

- General population of people with permanent residence in the country/study areas.
- Age group 0-79 years.
- Optional, depending on the substance of interest: specific occupational groups or hot-spots based on known pollutant concentrations.

HES

- At least: All persons aged 25-64 years and having permanent residence in the country
- Preferably also: 18+ years without upper age limit

Workshop on linking HBM and health studies,

Twitter: @HBM4EU, #HBM_HES, @tolonen_hanna

Exclusion criteria

HBM

- Depends on substances of interest

Sometimes exclusion criteria based on practical organization of study are set-up:

- Language skills
- Institutionalization

HES

- None

Workshop on linking HBM and health studies,

Twitter: @HBM4EU, #HBM_HES, @tolonen_hanna

Sampling frame

- Depends on national availability and legal possibility to use different sampling frames
- Ideally: central files with the most recent and best coverage of the target population

- Examples of sampling frames:

- Population register
- Census
- List of patients
- List of studies/employees
- Address list

Workshop on linking HBM and health studies,
14-15 June 2019, Brussels, Belgium

Twitter: @HBM4EU, #HBM_HES,
@tolonen_hanna

Sample size

HBM

- At least 500 per/country, depending on expected participation rate, i.e. data from at least 300 participants expected

HES

- At least 4,000 persons/country

Workshop on linking
HBM and health studies,

Twitter: @HBM4EU, #HBM_HES,
@tolonen_hanna

Eligibility criteria

Within defined age group, alive and still living in the study area

Workshop on linking HBM and health studies,
14-15 June 2019, Brussels, Belgium

Twitter: @HBM4EU, #HBM_HES,
@tolonen_hanna

Sampling scheme

- Two-stage sampling
- PSU: Study area/geographical area
- SSU: People, addresses, household or dwelling depending on available sampling frame

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@tolonen_hanna

Expected participation rate

HBM

• 60%

HES

• 70%

Aiming for as high participation rate as possible to avoid non-response bias on obtained results

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Twitter: @HBM4EU, #HBM_HES, @tolonen_hanna

Precision vs accuracy

Precision = variation of repeated measurements of the value of interest, i.e. how wide the sampling distribution is, which can be expressed as the standard deviation of the sampling distribution

Accuracy = difference between measured value and actual value in target population, i.e. how close the mean of the sampling distribution is to the mean of the population distribution (bias)

Performance of an estimator

Precision

Accuracy

Increase in sample size, increases precision

Increase in response rate, increases accuracy

Kulesa et al. Nature Methods 2015

Workshop on linking HBM and health studies, 14-15 June 2019, Brussels, Belgium

Twitter: @HBM4EU, #HBM_HES, @tolonen_hanna

Obtaining high participation rate

Questionnaire design

Timing and length of the visit

Incentives

Access to the examination clinic

Workshop on linking HBM and health studies,
14-15 June 2019, Brussels, Belgium

Twitter: @HBM4EU, #HBM_HES,
@tolonen_hanna

Recruitment of participants

- Recruitment strategy need to be adjusted for study design, target population, available funds, previous experience.
- Plan before hand and prepare realistic budget.
- Include
 - Publicity of the study
 - Format and timing of contact attempts
 - Supporting materials
 - Incentives

Workshop on linking HBM and health studies,
14-15 June 2019, Brussels, Belgium

Twitter: @HBM4EU, #HBM_HES,
@tolonen_hanna

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More information: HBM4EU D11.1 Report on opportunities and obstacles of combining HBM and health studies, availability of health studies with biological samples, availability of administrative registers, and guidelines for combining HBM and health studies. Part D. Guidelines for linking HBM and health studies

Speaker's information

Hanna Tolonen, PhD, Adjunct Professor, works as Research manager at the National Institute for Health and Welfare, Finland. She received training in statistics, public health and epidemiology. In HBM4EU she is a member of the Management Board and the Ethics Board, and the leader of WP11 Linking HBM, health surveys and registers.

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6.6.3 Questionnaires

Ana Virgolino from the Faculty of Medicine of the University of Lisbon (FMUL), Portugal, presented the questionnaire study performed under Task 7.1 of the HBM4EU Initiative to map concluded, ongoing or planned projects or activities related to human biomonitoring (HBM).

In the last decades, there has been a spawn of the complexity of contemporary HBM questions with large number of possible competing ideas for research. The growth in the scientific production in the area of HBM imposes the need for systematic methods for mapping the existing evidence in order to identify data gaps.

In this context, the use of questionnaires, and more specifically online questionnaires, is a suitable alternative tool for such a review. The internet and social and mobile networks' coverage is now significant which allows rapid dissemination of online questionnaires and reach of a large number of subjects, even when they are geographically widely dispersed (which assures a higher response rate). Using online questionnaires also facilitates the submission of answers, thus decreasing the associated costs and time in the process. Finally, the data collection and processing of results is simplified, requiring less time and effort.

The use of online questionnaires can have disadvantages as well, namely, in regards to the confidentiality of answers which cannot always be assured, the uncertainty about data validity or the sampling/representativeness of the answers. Moreover, respondents may face technical problems when accessing online questionnaires.

An online questionnaire was developed for Task 7.1 of the HBM4EU Initiative, aiming to map conducted (within last 10 years), ongoing or planned (starting within the next 5 years) studies, projects or activities (including available biobank samples). The questionnaire was developed based on a literature review to identify main areas and contents related to HBM, being then validated through partners' consultation. The dissemination of the questionnaire was done through the National Hub Contact Points, by the National Hub Coordinator.

Between March 28 and June 8, 2017, 124 replies were received. In terms of statistical analysis, univariate statistics and stratified analysis by region and groups of substances were performed.

The main results can be consulted on the [HBM4EU website](#) – Deliverable D7.1.

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QUESTIONNAIRES

Commonalities and differences
between HBM and
health studies

Ana Virgolino

HUMAN BIOMONITORING RESEARCH

Recent trends

Number of published papers:
'Human Biomonitoring' and *Biomonitoring*

HUMAN BIOMONITORING RESEARCH

Future directions for knowledge production

Spawn of the complexity of contemporary **HBM questions** with large number of possible competing ideas for research

Lack of integrated information for the production of adequate knowledge

Need for **systematic methods** for reviewing and mapping evidence & for identifying existing research gaps

HUMAN BIOMONITORING RESEARCH

Our challenge

Identification of existing data and data gaps in HBM

Building an online open access questionnaire, accessible to the HBM4EU partners

HUMAN BIOMONITORING RESEARCH

Our challenge

It is easy to develop a questionnaire but is not easy to develop a good questionnaire.

- Hill and Hill (1998) -

HUMAN BIOMONITORING RESEARCH

Our challenge

Guess who?

You are a character from a cartoon but you don't know which one.

You have to guess who you are only by asking the others "Yes" or "No" questions.

Try to find out who you are with the fewest number of questions.

Adapted from A. Biscaia (2014)

HUMAN BIOMONITORING RESEARCH

PAPER OR ONLINE QUESTIONNAIRES?

HUMAN BIOMONITORING RESEARCH

PAPER OR ONLINE QUESTIONNAIRES?

HUMAN BIOMONITORING RESEARCH

Online questionnaires

Advantages

- Diversity of questions
- Possibility of application to a large number of subjects, even if dispersed geographically (↑ answer rate)
- Automated submission of the questionnaire (↓ costs and time)
- Simplified collection and processing of results (less time and effort)

HUMAN BIOMONITORING RESEARCH

Online questionnaires

Advantages

- Diversity of questions
- Possibility of applying to a large number of subjects, even if dispersed geographically (↑ answer rate)
- Automated submission of the questionnaire (↓ costs and time)
- Simplified collection and processing of results (less time and effort)

Disadvantages

- Confidentiality of answers
- Uncertainty about data validity (false identity, multiple e-mails)
- Sampling/representativeness problems
- Technical problems to access the questionnaire (spam, lack of expertise of the respondents, technological variations)

QUESTIONNAIRE ON EXISTING HBM SURVEYS

Main goal

To map concluded (within last 10 years), ongoing or planned (for starting up within the next 5 years) studies, projects or activities (including available biobank samples)

1. Identification of knowledge gaps

2. Identification of policy links to REACH

QUESTIONNAIRE ON EXISTING HBM SURVEYS

The path

Task 7.1
questionnaire on
existing surveys

QUESTIONNAIRE ON EXISTING HBM SURVEYS

The path

Literature review

Identification of the areas and contents of the questionnaire

QUESTIONNAIRE ON EXISTING HBM SURVEYS

The path

Literature review

Identification of the areas and contents of the questionnaire

Partners' consultation

Validation of the structure and contents of the questionnaire with task partners and other WP leaders

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QUESTIONNAIRE ON EXISTING HBM SURVEYS

Partners

Chemical Group Leaders (CGLs)
National Hub Coordinator (NHC)
National Hub Contact Points (NHCPs)

QUESTIONNAIRE ON EXISTING HBM SURVEYS

The path

Literature review

Identification of the areas and contents of the questionnaire

Partners' consultation

Validation of the structure and contents of the questionnaire with task partners and other WP leaders

Launch of the questionnaire

Consultation of the National Hub Contact Points (NHCPs) through the National Hub Coordinator (NHC)

QUESTIONNAIRE ON EXISTING HBM SURVEYS

Difficulties

Formulation of questions

Use of plain text for general population

Get agreement about technical terms between researchers from different areas/schools of knowledge

Study setting

① Please indicate the setting or environment in which the study took / will take place

- a. Occupational exposure study
- b. Hotspot area (e.g., study area located near industrial site or other known exposure source)
- c. Other (Please specify) _____

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QUESTIONNAIRE ON EXISTING HBM SURVEYS

Difficulties

Formulation of questions

Wide scope of questions

Coverage of different subjects:

From ethics to study design

From anthropometric measures to essential trace elements

Which data were collected regarding essential trace elements?

Which data were collected regarding anthropometry?

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QUESTIONNAIRE ON EXISTING HBM SURVEYS

Difficulties

Formulation of questions

Wide scope of questions

Reach the stakeholders

Questionnaire targeting
HBM4EU partners

What about other researchers
with established work in the
field but outside the HBM4EU
coverage?

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QUESTIONNAIRE ON EXISTING HBM SURVEYS

Main sections

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QUESTIONNAIRE ON EXISTING HBM SURVEYS

Results

Period of data collection

March 28 – June 8, 2017

Number of filled in questionnaires

124

Process of data analysis

- Univariate statistics
- Stratified analysis by region and groups of substances

QUESTIONNAIRE ON EXISTING HBM SURVEYS

Main results

FIGURE 1. Where data were/are/will be collected

QUESTIONNAIRE ON EXISTING HBM SURVEYS

Main results

TABLE 1. Study/project/activity implementation level

	Frequency (n)	Percent (%)
International	15	10,5
National	57	39,9
Regional (province, county, etc.)	65	45,5
Other	6	4,2
Total	143	100,0

QUESTIONNAIRE ON EXISTING HBM SURVEYS

Main results

TABLE 2. Status of country representative projects by European-defined region

Representative sample (n=79)	North n (%)	West n (%)	South n (%)	East n (%)	Other n (%)
Planned	0 (0,0)	2 (8,0)	4 (12,1)	0 (0,0)	1 (33,3)
Initiated/Ongoing	11 (73,3)	8 (32,0)	12 (36,4)	5 (62,5)	1 (33,3)
Concluded					
≤ 10 years ago	3 (20,0)	7 (28,0)	14 (42,4)	3 (37,5)	0 (0,0)
> 10 years ago	0 (0,0)	2 (8,0)	0 (0,0)	0 (0,0)	0 (0,0)
Not indicating how long ago	1 (6,7)	6 (24,0)	3 (9,1)	0 (0,0)	1 (33,3)

North: Denmark, Estonia, Finland, Iceland, Ireland, Latvia, Lithuania, Norway, Sweden, UK
 West: Austria, Belgium, France, Germany, Luxembourg, The Netherlands, Switzerland
 South: Croatia, Cyprus, Greece, Italy, Malta, Portugal, Slovenia, Spain
 East: Bulgaria, Czech Republic, Hungary, Poland, Romania, Slovakia
 Other: Israel

QUESTIONNAIRE ON EXISTING HBM SURVEYS

Main results

TABLE 3. Target population by European-defined region

	North n (%)	West n (%)	South n (%)	East n (%)	Other n (%)
Newborns	9 (32,1)	13 (29,5)	9 (20,5)	11 (68,8)	2 (28,6)
Children	16 (57,1)	26 (59,1)	24 (54,5)	14 (87,5)	4 (57,1)
Adolescents	7 (25,0)	13 (29,5)	6 (13,6)	4 (25,0)	0 (0,0)
Adults	19 (67,9)	18 (40,9)	24 (54,5)	9 (56,3)	5 (71,4)
Elderly	5 (17,9)	5 (11,4)	6 (13,6)	4 (25,0)	0 (0,0)

North: Denmark, Estonia, Finland, Iceland, Ireland, Latvia, Lithuania, Norway, Sweden, UK
 West: Austria, Belgium, France, Germany, Luxembourg, The Netherlands, Switzerland
 South: Croatia, Cyprus, Greece, Italy, Malta, Portugal, Slovenia, Spain
 East: Bulgaria, Czech Republic, Hungary, Poland, Romania, Slovakia
 Other: Israel

QUESTIONNAIRE ON EXISTING HBM SURVEYS

Main results

FIGURE 2. Substances under study

QUESTIONNAIRE ON EXISTING HBM SURVEYS

Main results

FIGURE 3. Biological samples collected

QUESTIONNAIRE ON EXISTING HBM SURVEYS

Main results

TABLE 4. Sharing of the questionnaire used for data collection

	Frequency (n)	Percent (%)
No	21	16,9
Yes, it is available to any researcher	43	34,7
Yes, only to HBM/EU partners	60	48,4
Total	124	100,0

QUESTIONNAIRE ON EXISTING HBM SURVEYS

Main results

QUESTIONNAIRE HBM AND HEALTH STUDIES

Some communalities

	HBM	HES
Anthropometric measurements	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Height Weight Waist circumference 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Height Weight Waist circumference Hip circumference Body composition by bioimpedance
Clinical measurements	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Blood pressure Osteodensitometry 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Blood pressure Lung function measurement Cognitive function test Physical activity/fitness test and measurements Ultrasound tests on thyroid and bone density
Biological measurements	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Volume of urinary creatinine Cotinine Iron status (blood ferritin and transferritin) Iodine status (T4, TSH) Glycated haemoglobin (HbA_{1c}) Biomarkers of renal dysfunction 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Total and HDL cholesterol Glycose if fasting samples collected otherwise glycated haemoglobin (HbA_{1c})

Source: Deliverable report 11.1

WHAT'S NEXT?

Inventory of existing HBM surveys

There is the need to continuously update the information about HBM to ensure the **sustainability** of initiatives such as HBM4EU

- Questionnaire adaptation into a repository continuously open
- NHCPs (via NHC) invitation to answer whenever they have new studies not yet included in the database

HUMAN BIOMONITORING RESEARCH

Conclusions

- Biomonitoring data can provide much-needed information on exposure to a variety of environmental chemicals

- Interpretation of existing biomonitoring data requires rigorous, scientific approaches to data collection, analysis, interpretation, and application

- The use of questionnaires (together with other approaches) is determinant for comprehensive gathering of research data

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Institute of Environmental
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Thank you!

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6.6.4 Collection of biological samples

Anna-Maria Andersson from the Rigshospitalet, Capital Region of Denmark, presented the commonalities and differences between HBM and health studies regarding the collection of biological samples.

In health studies, human samples are often collected with the aim of measuring different clinical biomarkers. Most commonly blood samples are collected but other matrices such as urine may also be included. As human biomonitoring (HBM) makes use of the same types of human samples, adding a HBM module to a planned or ongoing health study is an opportunity that allows taking advantage of an already established infrastructure for collecting, handling, and storing samples for subsequent analysis. However, to ensure that the collected samples and hence the subsequent HBM results are representative of the population to be studied and not biased by the setting, in which the samples were collected, there are some considerations that need to be addressed. Considerations related to the pre-sampling conditions include, whether the sampling scheme established for the health study could bias the samples in some way. As an example, study subjects may be fasting before sample collection because fasting samples are required for the measurement of certain clinical markers. In such situations, it needs to be considered how this may affect the concentration of the analyte(s) investigated for HBM. In cases like this, it may be better to collect the samples for HBM at another time point.

A very important issue for HBM is to avoid contamination of the collected samples during collection, handling in the laboratory or during storage. This is an issue especially for HBM regarding analytes which are likely to be present in and leaking from laboratory equipment including materials for collecting and storing samples or just commonly present in e.g. house dust and air. For such analytes, there is a risk that they could be transferred to the sample during or after collection and result in false increased levels that do not represent the actual in vivo levels. The risk of contamination of samples can be minimized by checking the used laboratory equipment and consumables for leaking and replace them if necessary and possible. However, if HBM is linked to health studies, it may not always be realistic to replace equipment that may be problematic from a HBM point of view if it has been selected based on the requirements of the health study.

To be able to estimate and at least to partly control for potential contamination of collected samples, it is very useful to collect so-called "field blank samples". Field blank samples are aliquots of a clean matrix (e.g. analytical grade water or ethanol (or mix of these)), which are treated in exactly the same way as the biological samples. Collection of field blank samples can be especially valuable when it is not known a priori, which analytes are going to be measured. It is highly recommended that a field blank sample is collected (i.e. handled together with the biological samples) at least at 2-3 different time points during a study. How many and how often field blank samples should be collected may depend on how standardized the procedures for sampling and handling of biological samples are.

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Commonalities and
differences between HBM
and health studies:

Collection of biological samples

Anna-Maria Andersson

Rigshospitalet
Region Hovedstaden, Denmark
Edmarc.net

Types of samples

Health studies	
Blood	blood cell counts, analytical clinical chemistry (e.g. lipids, HbA1c, hormones and other clinical markers), DNA
Urine	e.g. proteinuria, sugar, sodium intake, infections, drugs
Faeces	e.g. microbiom diversity
Saliva	e.g. measurement of hormones and selected clinical markers

Photos: Colourbox

Types of samples

Health studies		HBM	
Blood	blood cell counts, analytical clinical chemistry (e.g. lipids, HbA1c, hormones and other clinical markers), DNA	Blood	e.g. POPs, metals/trace elements, organic compounds, drugs
Urine	e.g. proteinuria, sugar, sodium intake, infections, drugs	Urine	e.g. metals/trace elements, metabolites, organic compounds, drugs
Faeces	e.g. microbiom diversity	Faeces	(incl. meconium)
Saliva	e.g. measurement of hormones and selected clinical markers	Saliva	e.g. metals/trace elements, organic compounds, POPs
		Breastmilk	
		Hair	
		Nails	

1/3/2017

Types of samples

Matrix	Advantage	Disadvantage
Blood Serum plasma	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> in equilibrium with organs and tissues widely studied and well established SOPs for sampling 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Invasive volume limitation
Urine	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> non-invasive no volume limitation metabolite analysis 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> large urinary dilution variability
Faeces	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> non-invasive no volume limitation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> less documented for HBM applications
Saliva	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> non-invasive 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> volume limitation lower levels, sensitive methods needed less documented for HBM applications
Hair & nails	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> non-invasive easy storage and transport information about short and long term exposure (segmental analysis) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> difficulty in differentiating internal/external exposure hair: potential variations with colour, hair care or race
Breast milk	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> non-invasive information about mother and child enriched in lipophilic compounds 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> restricted to certain period of life deuration during lactation to be considered in interpretation

1/3/2017

Considerations:

- **Are the collected samples representative for biomonitoring purposes?**
- **Is the integrity of the analyte(s) in the sample secured during sampling, handling and storage?**

1/3/2017

Pre-sampling conditions

	Health Studies	HBM
Fasting	Overnight or 8-10 h. fasting required e.g. for measurement of triglycerides or fasting glucose in serum	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • fasting at the time of sampling may result in bias towards lower levels, especially for non-persistent compounds as food and drink are important sources of exposure for many chemicals • serum lipids affected by fasting • bias in time of the day in sampling

1/3/2017

Pre-sampling conditions: Fasting

Phillips et al. Arch. Environ. Contam. Toxicol. 18, 493-500 (1989)

1/3/2017

Pre-sampling conditions: Fasting

Phillips et al. Arch. Environ. Contam. Toxicol. 18, 493-500 (1989)

1/3/2017

Pre-sampling conditions: Fasting

Phillips et al. Arch. Environ. Contam. Toxicol. 18, 493-500 (1989)

1/3/2017

Pre-sampling conditions: Fasting

[Effect of fasting on urinary BPA levels](#)

Results of a 48 hour fasting study

Christensen et al. Environ Int. 2012, 50:7-14.

1/3/2017

Other pre-sampling considerations

- **Collection of biological specimens in medical settings**

1/3/2017

Other pre-sampling considerations

Example:
Prospective study of chemicals in
maternal and fetal compartments

Yan et al. *Ecol Risk Assess.* 2009, 15:565-578

Metabolites	Subjects	50th
MMP	NJ women	<LODa
	US female	1.30
MEP	NJ women	169
	US female	167
MBP	NJ women	14.8
	US female	21.6
MIBP	NJ women	4.60
	US female	2.50
MBzP	NJ women	9.15
	US female	15.4
MCPP	NJ women	1.55
	US female	3.00
MEHP	NJ women	115
	US female	4.10
MEHHP	NJ women	109
	US female	18.2
MEOHP	NJ women	95.1
	US female	13.0

1/3/2017

Other pre-sampling considerations

- **Collection of biological specimens in medical settings**
- **Medicine use**
- **Week-day vs. week-end, seasonal variation, diurnal variation**

1/3/2017

Sampling, processing and storage

	Health studies	HBM
Sampling and storage equipment	selected based on medical/clinical or clinical biochemistry criteria	risk of contamination of samples during collection/handling/storage has to be considered

1/3/2017

Photos: Colourbox

Recommendations

- Test *a priori* possible contamination sources in the collection, handling and storage settings
- If possible substitute identified contamination sources
- Record parameters related to collection and processing of samples
- **Include field blank samples**

1/3/2017

Field blank sample

A high-purity solution that is subjected to all aspects of sample collection, field-processing preservation, transportation, and laboratory handling as the specimen samples

1/3/2017

Sampling conditions

Example:
Measurement of chemicals in amniotic fluid

Sampling during ultrasound assisted amniocentesis

1/3/2017

- All equipment tested *a priori* for potential leaking of the chemicals to be studied.
- The ultrasound gel, used in connection to ultrasound guided amniocentesis contained n-PrP but could not be replaced.
- Field blank samples confirmed that the ultrasound gel was a source of contamination

Conclusions:

Collected human samples can often be used for both measurement of clinical biomarkers and exposure biomarkers

- Record conditions for sampling and handling for future records (e.g. detailed sample collection and handling protocols, date/time of sampling, equipment used)
- Include field blank samples

1/3/2017

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6.6.5 Objective health measurements

Loïc Rambaud and Romuald Tagne-Fotso from Santé publique France presented relevant objective health measurements for combined HBM and health survey.

Objective health measurement can be defined as a measure of health status which is quantifiable and independent of individual experience. Within health studies, objective health measurements are commonly divided into physical and biological measurements. The physical measurement category includes anthropometric measurements (height, weight, etc.) and clinical measurements (blood pressure, etc.). Biological measurements consist of analysis of biological materials (matrix) to describe human body metabolic activity, which is very similar to what is done in human biomonitoring studies for assessing chemical substance exposure levels.

Objective health measurements are used for different reasons in health examination surveys (HES) and in HBM studies. In HES, health measurements allow the assessing of prevalence of diseases and identifying risk factors and, if surveys are repeated over time, measuring changes for assessing public health policies. In HBM studies, health measurements are more often used for a better interpretation of chemical substance exposure levels and for eventually linking these levels with a possible health effect.

In order to select the most relevant objective health measurements for combined HES and HBM studies, we established a list of criteria. This was based on the list that was defined previously in EHES for HESs only and includes public health importance, clear interpretation of results, availability of international standards, practicability, being the only source of information, cost of survey, and ethical and participant acceptability. For combined HBM/HES studies, and in order to take into account HBM needs, we added four criteria: the sensibility to express potential graded health effect, the matrix compatibility, the existing data from previous HBM/HES studies and the potential for biomarker of effect. These criteria should be used to prioritize objective health measurements in combined HES/HBM studies.

As a recommendation, to build a combined HES/HBM survey, the investigators should at least integrate height, weight, waist circumference, blood pressure, volume of urinary creatinine (or specific gravity), cholesterol and glucose as mandatory health measurements. Some optional measurements can be added in order to more closely fulfil the needs of HES as for examples osteodensitometry, physical activity, iron or iodine status, nutritional status, etc.

Even if the aims of HES and HBM components may be very different, the opportunity to mutualize sampling procedure, recruitment, fieldwork operations, and trained personnel for performing health measurements and to collect biological samples should be taken into account when studied populations are the same.

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Commonalities and differences between HBM and health studies : Objective health measurements

*Workshop : Linking HBM and health studies.
What are possible opportunities and obstacles ?
Brussels, June 15th 2018*

Loïc Rambaud (loic.rambaud@santepubliquefrance.fr), Romuald Tagne-Fotso

Objective health measurements

- Anthropometric measurements
 - For measuring human body morphology
 - *ex : Height, weight, waist or hip circumferences*
- Clinical (or physical) measurements
 - For assessing human body functionality
 - *ex : Blood pressure, cognitive function tests*
- Biological measurements
 - For assessing human body metabolic activity
 - *ex : Cholesterol, creatinine, iodine status*

Aims and needs for health measurements

- Health Studies (HES)
 - Asses prevalence of major diseases and risk factors
 - Measure changes in time and assess health policies
- Human Biomonitoring Studies (HBM)
 - Better interpretation of results
 - Links between exposure and possible health effects

15/06/2018

Commonalities and differences

Anthropometric measurements

	HBM	HES
Mandatory	Height Weight	Height Weight Waist circumference
Optional	Waist circumference	Hip circumference Body composition

15/06/2018

Commonalities and differences

Clinical (or physical) measurements

	HBM	HES
Mandatory		Blood pressure
Optional	Blood pressure Osteodensitometry	Physical activity Respiratory function Cognitive function Thyroid function Osteodensitometry Dental examination Ophthalmology

15/06/2018

Commonalities and differences

Biological measurements

	HBM	HES
Mandatory	Urinary creatinine Cotinine	Cholesterol (LDL/HDL) Glucose (or glycated haemoglobin)
Optional	Iron status Iodine status Glycated haemoglobin Biomarkers of effects	Iron status, ferritin Iodine status Triglycerides Folates Vitamin D Apolipoproteins A1 and B DNA extraction Antibodies

15/06/2018

Selection of objective health measurements

- Criteria already defined in EHES
 - Public health importance
 - Clear interpretation of results
 - Availability of international standards
 - Practicality
 - No other source of information
 - Cost of the survey
 - Ethical acceptability
 - Participant acceptability
- In addition for HBM/HES combined studies
 - Sensibility to express potential health effect
 - Matrice compatibility
 - Existing data on previous HES/HBM studies
 - Potential for biomarker of effect

15/06/2018

Combining HBM and HES

- Different aims and needs for Objective Health Measurements but same type of population study for public health interest
- Opportunity to mutualise sampling, recruitment, fieldwork organization, trained personnel, etc.
- Reducing costs at country or European level
- Maximizing the possibility to get standardized data
- Need for SOPs adaptation

15/06/2018

Recommendations

- Combined studies should include mandatory health measurements
 - Height, weight, waist circumference, blood pressure, volume of urinary creatinine, cholesterol and glycosylated haemoglobin.
- Optional measurements in order to fit more HES needs
- Mutualisation of visit for collecting objective health measurement and biological samples

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Thank You

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6.7 Available training

6.7.1 Training on HBM issues

Paul T.J. Scheepers, leader of the Task 2.5 Training, from Radboudumc, Nijmegen, the Netherlands, presented training activities of HBM4EU.

Training is vital component of the HBM4EU initiative as it provides structure to the existing knowledge base and evolution of the state-of-knowledge on developments in different WPs. Training is also much about bringing this knowledge into practice and involving expertise of experienced persons in the programme. The objective of the training programme is to deliver effective training targeted at the needs of the HBM4EU community, with the aim of building capacities and promoting a coordinated approach to HBM across Europe.

To gather information on the needs for training, an online questionnaire was completed by 210 respondents from 26 countries in 2017. Most of the respondents had 0–5 years of experience in HBM (63%) and a majority of the respondents were interested in basic training (71%). The interest in advanced training topics was also considerable (32% for non-specific generic topics and 45% for specific topics). Trainings occasions of 1–3 days were preferred and most of the respondents indicated that they would like to participate in about two training activities per year. As a preparation for the course, self-study with online materials was preferred. Furthermore, the respondents would like to have a training occasion before and another one after the summer break. There was no preference for the location of the training, although most respondents indicated that they preferred less than 4 hours' travel time. The first training will be organized in June 18–22, 2018 in Ljubljana, Slovenia, as a training school with a two-day basic course followed by five one-day advanced level courses.

HBM4EU project

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Training on HBM issues
Paul T.J. Scheepers PhD
Task leader WP2.5 training

Objective of WP2.5

To deliver an effective training programme targeted at the needs of the HBM4EU community, with the aim of building capacities and promoting a coordinated approach to HBM across Europe

15/06/2018

Aim

Define optimal contents and format for training based on Training Needs (NEEDS) and available Knowledge, Expertise and Skills (KES).

Expected result:

Pre-announcement of the 2018 training programme the HBM4EU website

15/06/2018

QNEEDS: training needs

63 %
of the respondents
reported to have
between
0 and 5 years
of experience in the
field of HBM

15/06/2018

QNEEDS: training needs

<i>Training needs</i>	Basic	Advanced
General	34 %	32 %
Specific	25 %	45 %

91 % of the respondents is interested to follow a general basic course that covers all the basics.

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QNEEDS: training needs

Topics of interest stated by
> 20 % of respondents:

For most topics both basic and
advanced training are requested

For ethics and statistics
only basic training is requested

Ethics issues

Communication of study outcome

Development of population-based HBM-surveys

Method & Study protocol development and quality assurance

Data collection incl. privacy protection

Sample collection, shipment, short-term storage

Laboratory analysis

Interpretation of biomarker data

PBPK-modelling

Statistical analysis

15/06/2018

QKES: available expertise

n = 184

71 % of the respondents
report > 10 y of experience
in human biomonitoring

69 %

Theoretical knowledge

61 %

Practical expertise

34 %

Skills to demonstrate and
support hands-on training

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QKES: available expertise

Experience reported
by > 20% of respondents:

- Communication related to recruitment
- Communication of study outcome
- Development of population-based HBM-surveys
- Method & Study protocol development and quality assurance
- Data collection incl. privacy protection
- Sample collection, shipment, short-term storage
- Sample pre-treatment
- Laboratory analysis
- Interpretation of biomarker data
- PBPK-modelling
- Statistical analysis

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Preliminary proposal for 2018

MON BASIC	TUE BASIC	WED ADVANCED TOPIC-1	THU ADVANCED TOPIC-2	FRI ADVANCED TOPIC-3
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- One-week sessions at two different venues easy accessible by train/plane
- 2 sessions: one before and one after the summer
- Combination of basic and advanced training
- Basic training will be balanced to include the most relevant topics
- Topics for the advanced training come from QNEEDS
- Provide self-study materials in advance
- Individual and plenary evaluations will lead to modifications for 2019
- Participants will cover their own expenses for travel and accomodation

15/06/2018

QNEEDS: affinity of respondents

Objectives of the basic training

The basic training provides an overview of the most relevant aspects of HBM and wherever possible

specifically for HBM4EU at a basic level. We encourage participants to take their own projects ideas to the course. For some participants it may be possible to **apply some of the acquired knowledge and skills** immediately to implementation of national HBM4EU studies.

1st HBM4EU Training School

Programme

Date	Level	Code	Title
18-19 June	Basic	B01	HBM4EU basic training
20 June	Advanced	A01	Ethics
21 June	Advanced	A02	Data management and basics of data analysis
22 June	Advanced	A03	HBM in occupational health: applications to chromium
22 June	Advanced	A04	Quality requirements, validation and implementation of analytical methods in HBM programmes
22 June	Advanced	A05	Biomarkers of effect

1st HBM4EU Training School, Ljubljana, June 18-22, 2018

1st HBM4EU Training School

Learning objectives

Code and short title	Learning objectives
B01 Basic training	Applications of HBM in a societal context; Ethics implications and required approval of study protocols; Implement the harmonized HBM4EU methodology in own country
A01 Ethics	Overview of ethics requirements for HBM4EU studies and their application to his/her own HBM4EU study
A02 Data management	Integrate data collections into HBM4EU; how data are structured in the HBM4EU repository; to find, extract, and use the information and data that are available via IPCHEM
A03 Chromium study	Apply HBM in an occupational setting; knowledge and skills of sample collection methods for chromium
A04 Laboratory analysis	HBM4EU quality assurance and quality of collection and storage of samples, day-to-day maintenance and analytical methods used for chemical analysis in human samples
A05 Biomarkers of effect	Awareness of the use of biomarkers in research of gene-environment interactions

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HBM4EU training

Societal context

Topics of the basic training

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1st HBM4EU Training School

Registration

- Contact information
- Professional background
- Role in HBM4EU specified by WP number(s)
- Preference for courses B01-A01-A02-A03-A04-A05
- Level of knowledge/skills for each of course topics
- Need for interactive session (select from list of topics)
- Expectations [open field]
- Motivation [open field]
- Option to upload file (CV or recommendation letter)

1st HBM4EU Training School, Ljubljana, June 18-22, 2018

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1st HBM4EU Training School

Registration

Aspect	Number	Remark
Total applications submitted	56	Including 3 from experts also known as instructors
Not approved	5	2 incomplete; 3 too late
Eligible	51	Including 3 instructors
Canceled	5	1 travel problems; 2 work-related issues; 2 unknown
Expected to participate	46	

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1st HBM4EU Training School

Knowledge & Skills

1st HBM4EU Training School, Ljubljana, June 18-22, 2018

1st HBM4EU Training School

Topics for interaction

1st HBM4EU Training School, Ljubljana, June 18-22, 2018

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Advanced topics

Level for A03-A04-A05 topics

Before

After

1st HBM4EU Training School, Ljubljana, June 18-22, 2018

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HBM4EU training

Perspective

1. Input for training needs were used to determine content and format of 1st HBM4EU Training School
2. Evaluation will be used to adjust the content and form
3. Depending on input from WP and Pillar leads, the training content and format will be modified
4. More tailormade solutions are will be developed to respond to specific needs e.g. capacity building

1st HBM4EU Training School, Ljubljana, June 18-22, 2018

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Speaker's information

Paul T.J. Scheepers PhD works as associate professor at the Radboudumc, Nijmegen, The Netherlands. He received training in toxicology and occupational hygiene. In HBM4EU he is responsible for training activities as task leader in WP2. He is a member of the ethics board in WP1.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 733032.

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6.7.2 Training on health measurements

Hanna Tolonen from the National Institute for Health and Welfare (THL), Finland, presented the available training and capacity building activities for health measurements especially those provided under EHES.

Many of the objective health measurements, such as blood pressure, waist circumference, spirometry etc. are sensitive for deviations in the measurement protocol. For example blood pressure level can be affected due to sudden noise during the measurement, posture of the subject, wrongly selected blood pressure cuff size, etc. Also many people are sensitive for the measurement itself and suffer from white-coat hypertension.

To minimise potential variation in the measurement outcomes due to differences in measurement procedures, standardized protocols (SOPs) are needed as well as adequate training to accurately follow these protocols.

EHES has prepared SOPs for several health measurements on adults⁷ and also related training material⁸, which are freely available on the web. For children, similar SOPs are being prepared under WP11.

Hands on training of the health measurements are not currently provided under EHES due to the lack of resources.

⁷ Tolonen H (ed). EHES Manual. Part B. Fieldwork procedures. 2016. Available at <http://urn.fi/URN:ISBN:978-952-302-701-5>

⁸ http://www.ehes.info/training_materials/index.htm

Aim of training

- Key element of standardization and quality assurance
- Ensure that SOPs are followed correctly

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14-15 June 2019, Brussels, Belgium

Twitter: @HBM4EU, #HBM_HES,
@tolonen_hanna

Example – blood pressure

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@tolonen_hanna

Factors affecting blood pressure levels

- Measurement environment
 - Noise, temperature
- Factors related to the participant
- Factors related to the measurer
- Measurement device
 - Cuff size
- Factors related to measurement procedure

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14-15 June 2019, Brussels, Belgium

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Average magnitude of the participant effects

Effect	Systolic bp (mmHg)	Diastolic bp (mmHg)
Full bladder	↑ 10-15 mmHg, even up to 50 mmHg if bladder uncomfortably distended	↑ 10 mmHg, even up to 40 mmHg if bladder uncomfortably distended
Physical exercise before measurement	↓ 18-20 mmHg	↓ 7-8 mmHg
Heavy meal before measurement	↓ 20 mmHg	↓ 20 mmHg
Smoking before measurement	↑ 10-20 mmHg	↑ 8 mmHg

Tolonen H, Koponen P, Naska A et al. BMC Med Research Methodology 2013; 13:33. doi: 10.1186/s12874-013-0020-3

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Average magnitude of device effects

Effect	Systolic bp (mmHg)	Diastolic bp (mmHg)
Cuff too small	↑ 3-12 mmHg, in obese persons ↑ 30 mmHg	↑ 2-8 mmHg, in obese persons ↑ 30 mmHg
Cuff too large	↓ 10-30 mmHg	↓ 10-30 mmHg

Tolonen H, Koponen P, Naska A et al. BMC Med Research Methodology 2013; 13:33. doi: 10.1186/s12874-013-0020-3

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Twitter: @HBM4EU, #HBM_HES, @tolonen_hanna

Average magnitude of the effects related to measurement protocol (1/2)

Effect	Systolic bp (mmHg)	Diastolic bp (mmHg)
Not resting 3 to 5 minutes before measurement	↑ 10-20 mmHg	↑ 14 mmHg
Supine posture instead of sitting posture	↑ 3-10 mmHg	↑ 1-5 mmHg
Legs crossed	↑ 5-8 mmHg	↑ 3-5 mmHg
Back / feet unsupported	↑ 5-15 mmHg	↑ 6 mmHg
Left arm instead of right arm	↓ 1-3 mmHg	↑ 1 mmHg

Tolonen H, Koponen P, Naska A et al. BMC Med Research Methodology 2013; 13:33. doi: 10.1186/s12874-013-0020-3

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Average magnitude of the effects related to measurement protocol (2/2)

Effect	Systolic bp (mmHg)	Diastolic bp (mmHg)
Arm unsupported during the measurement	↑ 1-7 mmHg	↑ 5-11 mmHg
Arm below heart level	↑ 10 mmHg	↑ 10 mmHg
Participant talks during the measurement	↑ 10-15 mmHg	↑ 6-10 mmHg
Cuff over clothing	↑ 5 mmHg	Not reported

Tolonen H, Koponen P, Naska A et al. BMC Med Research Methodology 2015; 15:33. doi: 10.1186/s12874-015-0020-3

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@tolonen_hanna

EHES Training materials

- SOPs for anthropometric measurements, blood pressure, handgrip test, timed chair stand test and collection of biological samples (blood and urine) on adults
 - Published in the EHES Manual, Part B
- Related training material (PowerPoints) available freely on EHES web site

<http://www.ehes.info>

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@tolonen_hanna

Standardized measurement protocols and related quality control procedures

Anthropometrics

- Background information
- Height measurement
 - Measurement protocol
 - Quality control
- Weight measurement
 - Beam-balance scale
 - Measurement protocol
 - Electronic scale
 - Measurement protocol
 - Quality control
- Waist and hip circumference
 - Waist measurement protocol
 - Hip measurement protocol
 - Quality control

Blood pressure

- Mercury sphygmomanometer and other auscultation based devices
 - Background information
 - Measurement protocol
 - Quality control
- Automated devices
 - Background information
 - Measurement protocol
 - Quality control

Collection of biological samples

- Blood samples
 - Sample collection
 - Sample handling
 - Quality control
- Urine

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10

SOPs for children

- For selected set of objective health measurements
- Under preparation in WP11
- Some studies (HBM and HES) have already included health measurements for children
- Some HES specific SOPs available through EHES web site at <http://www.ehes.info/manuals.htm>

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Training on health measurements under HBM4EU

- EHES does not organize training seminars at the moment
- If partners of HBM4EU feel this would be needed, could be planned as part of HBM4EU training activities

Workshop on linking HBM and health studies,
14-15 June 2019, Brussels, Belgium

Twitter: @HBM4EU, #HBM_HES,
@tolonen_hanna

More information:

SOPs for health measurements on adults at the EHES Manual, Part B at

<http://urn.fi/URN:ISBN:978-952-302-701-5>

Training materials for these measurements at

<http://urn.fi/URN:ISBN:978-952-302-701-5>

Some SOPs for health measurements on children will be prepared under WP11 and published as D11.3 (M28) and D11.4 (M52)

Speaker's information

Hanna Tolonen, PhD, Adjunct Professor, works as Research manager at the National Institute for Health and Welfare, Finland. She received training in statistics, public health and epidemiology. She is the coordinator of the European Health Examination Survey (EHES). In HBM4EU she is a member of the Management Board and the Ethics Board, and the leader of WP11 Linking HBM, health surveys and registers.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 733032.

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7 Conclusions

As several examples have shown, combining HBM and health surveys is possible. However, it requires a lot of planning and work to be successful. A good overview of the most critical issues to consider when planning a combined HBM and health study was given in presentations during the workshop. It was also demonstrated that combining HBM and health studies has many benefits.

From the questionnaire launched by Task 11.1 on opportunities and obstacles for combining HBM and health studies, it became evident that there is a clear lack of knowledge, mainly among principle investigators of the health studies, about possibilities related to HBM measurements (Deliverable Report D11.1 Report on opportunities and obstacles of combining HBM and health studies, availability of health studies with biological samples, availability of administrative registers, and guidelines for combining HBM and health studies). Several studies reported lack of knowledge or capacities as a main reason why they had not included HBM measurements in their study. Lack of knowledge could be improved with better communication between HBM and health communities. For lack of resources, there is no simple and rapid solution.

Most commonly reported reasons for not including HBM measurements in a health study

- Lack of knowledge
 - on the relevance of measuring chemicals in relation to the aim of the study
 - regarding collection and handling of samples for measurement of chemicals
- Lack of funding for
 - additional sample collection required for measurement of chemicals
 - laboratory analysis of chemicals
- Lack of capacity available for measurement of chemicals (laboratories, methods etc.)
- Lack of storage space for additional samples
- Collection of additional samples for chemical measurements logistically not practical
- Fear that including HBM measurements would affect recruitment/participation rate

From provided presentations concerning studies where HBM and health studies had been combined, examples from Germany and Canada had similar approach. Both countries had facilitated existing national HESs and their infrastructure to execute a nationally representative HBM study as well. This had several benefits, which were raised up in both presentations.

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Benefits of combining HBM and health study

- Use on existing survey infrastructure on
 - recruitment of participants
 - collection of biological samples and conducting health examinations
 - collection of data with questionnaires including a wide range of topics (health, health behaviours, socio-economic position, exposure pathways etc.)
- Synergies in public relations activities during the fieldwork
- Reputation and awareness of the studies among the public
- Possibility to combine data on exposure, health behaviours, health and socio-economic position to large, comprehensive data sets
- Reduced costs of public resources

Combining two in many ways similar but yet different study types includes challenges as was demonstrated by German and Canadian examples.

Challenges in combining HBM and health study

- Partners involved in HBM and health studies may have different priorities. Finding a balanced compromise between them is often needed.
- Preparation phase may take a longer time due to the need for more negotiations, meetings, and agreements (rights, duties, sharing of costs, data protection and sharing, etc.).
- Target population, time lines, extent of the full survey etc. may be defined by the HES study. Accommodating a HBM part to this may be challenging.
- Volume of collected blood samples is limited. How is the use of the collected samples prioritised in relation to HBM and health parts' requirements?
- To minimize the burden on the participants the length of the questionnaire must be limited. On the other hand, it should include all relevant questions on both HBM and health issues.
- Coordination between HBM and health modules of the study.
- The large data sets with data on exposures and health that the combined studies result in are often underutilized.

In France, the combined HBM and health study was planned from the start to include both components for all participants. Therefore, some of the challenges faced when a HBM study is using HES infrastructure could be avoided in that case.

In the presentations from countries, which had conducted separate HBM or health studies but had no experience in conducting a combined HBM–health study, similar concerns regarding challenges were raised up as in those reported by countries, with had experience of a combined study. Additional concerns were raised up by UK/England related to handling and processing of biological samples in home settings. In Health Survey for England, nurse visits, during which also biological samples are collected, are conducted at the participants' homes. This is not a standardized setting for sample collection, handling and processing. It was also noted that due to the setting, participation rate in blood sample collection is lower than for surveys in general. Also if blood

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samples are to be collected from children, specially trained personnel would be required, which is significantly more expensive than regularly used survey nurses.

In Denmark, HBM studies are not carried out but regional/local HESs and other health studies are conducted regularly and biological samples are stored for future use. Use of these stored samples could be a starting point for HBM studies, especially since in Denmark a lot of additional information on individuals can be obtained through record linkage to administrative data sources.

All provided presentations concerning experiences from different countries or theoretical background information strongly support the feasibility of combining HBM and health studies. If it is not possible to conduct a HBM module among the entire national HES sample, which often is relatively large (4,000 persons and above), it should be considered if a HBM module among a sub-sample of participants would be sufficient. The collaboration between HBM and health communities could also start from the use of stored biological samples from health studies and slowly, as the knowledge increases, grow into full-size collaboration, which would cover all phases from planning to reporting.